

IN-HABIT – INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.1 DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION PLAN

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Status	Date	Contributor/partner	Summary of changes
V 0.1	Draft	22/01/2021	D. Bavuso, C. Marrone, S. Marrone (BOT)	Initial drafting
V 0.2	Draft	28/01/2021	D. Bavuso, C. Marrone, S. Marrone (BOT)	Advanced draft
V 0.3	Draft	10/02/2021	All PPs	Advanced draft, feedback
V 0.4	Draft	15/02/2021	D. Bavuso, D. Bordin, C. Marrone, S. Marrone (BOT)	Final draft, including collated feedback by PPs
V 0.5	Advanced draft	22/02/2021	ISIM, LCREA	Peer Reviewed
V 0.6	Final document	25/02/2021	BOT	Feedback included, language final revision

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CA	Consortium Agreement
DECO	Dissemination,Exploitation, Communication & Outreach
DC	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 projects
IHW	Inclusive Health and Wellbeing
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
RTD	Research, technology and development
SMSCs	Small and medium sized cities
WP	Work Package

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PARTNERS' SHORT NAMES

AVUE	Neighbourhood Association of Las Palmeras
BOT	Book on a Tree
BSC	Baltic Studies Centre
B4B	Bridge for Billions
CORD	Ayuntamiento de Córdoba
DFC	Design for Change Spain
HIDE	Hidepark Civic Association Triptych
ISIM	isIMPACT
KQ	Kalniciema Quarter
LABORELEC	Engie Laborelec
LCREA	Lucca Crea
LUCCA	Comune di Lucca
NITRA	Mesto Nitra
PUJ	Pontificia Universidad Javeriana
RIGA	Riga Planning Region
SUA	Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra
TSR	Tesseræ

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UCO	University of Cordoba
UNIPI	Universita di Pisa
UREAD	University of Reading
WTG	WellnessTechGroup

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document represents a **Dissemination and Communication (DC) Plan** and a comprehensive **Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) strategy** including all the guidelines and actions related to the INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies (IN-HABIT) project objectives as well as an overview of the various communication strategies, messages and expected key performance indicators (KPIs).

The strategy includes **web, social media, print, audio-visual and digital tools** which will be adapted to reach the IN-HABIT relevant target audiences. Tracking and monitoring of these activities will enable the impact of the communication and dissemination activities to be measured.

The communication strategy is tightly coupled with the dissemination activities, given that the focus from the start will be on **creating awareness** by publicising the project in the cities and beyond.

To multiply the impact and adapt the communication efforts, partners will use their local media and own communication channels to **disseminate project results** and **engage with local actors**. Each partner is responsible for identifying local stakeholders in its city/country and ensuring that the project communication reaches the largest possible number of targeted actors at a local level. Other city and international levels will be also targeted through city networks and relevant events.

An initial version of the DC plan will be issued in M6, but the plan will be a living document that will evolve during the project's lifetime. **An addendum taking into account specific local needs emerging from the stakeholder mapping and training activities with community activators and observers, plus the work with local key contacts, will be developed** by M12. The DC will be updated throughout the duration of the project based on periodic DECO Committee decisions. Each time the document is updated, all partners will be duly informed.

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In addition, the DC will be stored in the internal repository of IN-HABIT documents, ensuring access to all partners.

The IN-HABIT Project

IN-HABIT (INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies) is an EU Horizon 2020 project that aims to foster inclusive health and wellbeing (IHW) in small and medium size cities (SMSCs). **In each of the four pilot cities, the project will mobilise existing undervalued resources to increase health and wellbeing**, with a focus on gender, diversity, equity and inclusion (GDE&I).

The integrated approach will combine technological, digital, nature-based, cultural and social innovations in selected urban public spaces. These solutions will be co-designed, co-deployed and co-managed with and by local stakeholders. The project will run for five years, from September 2020 to August 2025.

The Team

The IN-HABIT consortium is a **multidisciplinary team** of twenty-one partners from seven European countries (Spain, Italy, Latvia, Slovakia, United Kingdom, Germany, Belgium) and Colombia. The team is made up of universities and other high-level research organisations, city representatives, grass-roots partners, other small or medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and non-profit organisations.

The Cities

The IN-HABIT project is focusing on four peripheral SMSCs across Europe: **Cordoba** (Spain), **Riga** (Latvia), **Lucca** (Italy) and **Nitra** (Slovakia). IN-HABIT's actions in each city aim to foster inclusive health and wellbeing by integrating solutions around four main values: **Heritage & Culture, Food, Animals, Art & Environment**. Moreover, the involvement of Bogota will extend the option to interact with the CELAC region.

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SCENARIO

The IN-HABIT project was born in a year characterised by many changes that have **revolutionised** the uses, the possibilities of communication and social interaction and the working methods, impacting the ability of some events to have a prominent offline event capable of generating exchange, affection, interaction and networking. The regulation resulting from the need to stem the COVID-19 pandemic has **prevented demonstrations and events** around the world from taking place, including the most important and symbolic ones. To date, it is not yet clear what will happen in the next year and if this will allow us to return to the previous meeting and communication habits. However, what is certain is that the opportunity for offline events to be successful is also linked to people's **trust in taking part**, as well as the effective ability of those who promote and host them to **guarantee safety conditions** according to current regulations, taking on specific responsibilities, and local and national limitations and regulations about meetings and gatherings (i.e., limitations on number of people meeting, or adequate spaces) put in place by authorities.

The unpredictability of events due to COVID-19 impacts the IN-HABIT project because it makes it more difficult to understand whether the physical events, which have objectives linked to the fundamental mission of the project (promoting inclusion, wellbeing), will be able to take place. In this phase of the project, however, it is important to be able to plan the organisation of such events also by reason of evaluation of the resources to be allocated that cannot be postponed. For this reason, to make planning more linear, **a more digital approach to events** is proposed for 2021.

The digital approach allows participation in the project's initiatives to be extended to anyone who would have been unable to participate for various reasons (in addition to those attributable to security measures for COVID-19). In addition to this, much of the communication of the project and the partner projects, and much of the information regarding the progress of European cities and the world in moving towards more sustainable logics is

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currently found on the web and spreads through digital channels, becoming engaging thanks to the supported formats (videos, podcasts, etc.), which fit into people's daily lives by involving them on topics – which may not be their first selection – even if only thanks to captivating storytelling and an accessible and usable format. For this reason, the digital world gives the information concerning the project a greater opportunity to be shared and spread more easily and reach otherwise unthinkable recipients, guaranteeing a profound dissemination and superior opportunities to multiply the message. Of course, facing the digital divide is expected at an early stage of the project, especially since there are many people who for various reasons do not access digital every day and, locally, this criticality is planned to be managed with the support of those who participate in the project (for example, at a local level, through the interpretation of customs, habits and social peculiarities in the four cities where the experimentation takes place).

More information on the use of digital channels will be covered in further detail in this document in chapter 2.

This choice presents the challenge of thinking of new ways to allow the **participation of inhabitants and stakeholders** in this project for which accessibility and inclusion are key values: many of the recipients of this project do not have access to digital devices (tablets and PCs) for various reasons and are at risk of being excluded. This plan will then illustrate how communication and project activities can be **designed in an inclusive way** by developing the approach to mainstream tools and channels and bringing project communication into containers and formats that are familiar and widespread among the targets, perhaps for other purposes (education, information, communication between peers, entertainment).

At the same time, **encouraging inhabitants to act through digital channels**, providing them with the tools and supporting them to develop the necessary skills, is itself configured as an action oriented towards inclusion, being aimed at an empowerment that impacts their overall capacity to access information inside and outside the project and to interact in a modern way

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with the world around them, seizing the opportunities that require basic knowledge of these channels and tools.

Another aspect related to the accessibility of the opportunities given participating in the project concerns the linguistic and cultural gap that will be addressed by planning a **multi-channel communication**, in specific cases declined in the languages spoken in the IN-HABIT cities and operated with the support of local community activators and observers.

Addressing a critical scenario all together also requires an extension of responsibility: with the help of local community activators first, and then observers, it is expected that the project will be able to propose communication activities and **enable the use of digital channels**. **These events** would participate in **achieving the objective of inclusion** in the project but also in the long term for categories at risk of exclusion/ disadvantage. The project would be talked about, how to take action would be explained to the individuals and in doing so they would be trained digitally, thus prolonging the effect of their ability to remain included beyond the terms of the project and generating in them the desire to continue to contribute later.

Also, to **maximise the impact** of the effort put into training activities and at the same time **empower local supporters**, a second life of each training activity related to WP8 will already be defined by the planning phase (e.g., the training done in the classroom will then possibly be made accessible to other targets online, on mobile phones, in other formats, also taking care not to generate new efforts along the project tasks).

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1. IN-HABIT communications objectives

The activities included in WP8 of the Grant Agreement aim to contribute to the **effective communication** of the project and its results, engaging internal and external targets. Here, the internal targets are the main core Project Partners and the external ones all those who, even if over time will be involved and will help to support it with their actions, in an initial phase are not to be considered active promoters: mainstream audiences, scientific communities, and decision-makers from a local to global level, such as the decision-makers, at various institutional levels, who in other parts of the world may decide to adopt the approaches tested by IN-HABIT by projecting cities, regions, districts and peri-urban areas in a dimension of wellbeing and inclusion, encouraging active support.

All the activities within this plan are essential for **raising public awareness** about the importance of fostering inclusive health and wellbeing in small and medium size cities, starting from undervalued resources and from an approach where **cooperation is fundamental** to allowing the integration of technologies, digital, nature-based solutions, cultural and social innovations for the creation of valuable inclusive urban public spaces.

According to the European Commission (EC) Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms,

“Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about the action and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”

The EC Glossary also provides a definition for dissemination, that is:

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“The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”

These two definitions are a starting point for this DC plan and DECO strategy, where activities related to communication, dissemination and outreach can **overlap and interplay**. The plan shows the strategy, objectives and related actions, monitoring systems and measurable KPIs to assess the impact of the project in its different phases, recommendations for the use of each channel, and risks and mitigation measures, also including:

- the project visual identity and respective tools;
- communication guidelines;
- relevant EC references;
- a project glossary developed in cooperation with the project partner (PP) TSR in WP5.

Moreover, the communication among the main players of the project will include:

- **vertical communication (bidirectional)**, through which the coordinators of WP8 will support partners, local activators and observers with input and operational indications on the activities that implement the strategy and through which feedback and information from local or grassroots activities reach the coordinator allowing strategic fine-tuning;
- **internal peer communication**, which will support the exchange of materials, information and feedback in order to guarantee a strategy that exploits all the opportunities for visibility and contextualisation of the contents useful for external communication;
- **external peer communication**, through which all the external targets will be informed, engaged and involved in the project.

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Moreover, this is a **living document**, and it will be updated yearly throughout the duration of the project, starting from the partners' feedback and focusing in particular on the impact of the strategy.

Yearly, as required by the corresponding reporting actions, and at the end of the project, a **final report** will summarise actions, efforts and values provided by the partners in relation to the whole DECO strategy.

1.1 Project objectives (POs)

The IN-HABIT project aims to craft a future based on **high quality, multifunctional, public spaces** able to integrate digital, social, cultural and nature-based innovation to **enhance health and wellbeing**, while ensuring 'the right to the city' as specified in the UN's Habitat III New Urban agenda (adopted at the United Nations Conference on Housing and Sustainable Urban Development (Habitat III) in Quito, Ecuador, on 20 October 2016 and endorsed by the United Nations General Assembly at its sixty-eighth plenary meeting of the seventy-first session on 23 December 2016).

1.1.1 A local field of action

At the end of the project, several multifunctional urban public spaces will be regenerated: a green and sustainable **mobility** corridor and a green and creative central square in a deprived neighbourhood in Cordoba; a **food market area** in the Āgenskalns district of Riga; two urban **parks** reorganised to support human-animal interactions in Lucca; a **multifunctional cycling corridor** in Nitra. The quality of these urban spaces will improve Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW) in terms of green space availability, safety, accessibility, resilience, and inclusiveness, increasing the capacity to respond to mobility, recreational, security and socio-economic needs of excluded groups. The deployment of visionary and integrated

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solutions (VIS) will thus **enhance liveability** of these public spaces for local citizens. IN-HABIT's urban planning paradigm focused on IHW as urban commons will thus contribute to establishing a compensation mechanism that re-distributes the above mentioned "Right to the city". Protected characteristics (PCs) – nationality, sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age, sexual orientation will be central to the measures of the KPIs.

1.1.2 A global framework of thinking

The smaller size of the municipalities also permits a closer interaction between them and silo breaking actions to foster **systemic and innovative urban planning**. The EU is also fully committed to major global urban agreements such as the UN Habitat's New Urban Agenda, the Global Covenant of Mayors, the Urban Agenda for the EU and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030.

These agendas put the focus on **the role of cities** in addressing systemic global challenges and their relevance in managing the transition towards sustainable development. IN-HABIT will contribute to the main objectives of these agendas, providing research on how SMSCs work in practice and delivering a **European model** of integrated social, cultural, digital, and nature-based innovations that can be applied to urban space regeneration and progress worldwide.

Additionally, IN-HABIT results will feed the claim launched in the World Urban Forum 2030 Declaration to tackle all inequalities and especially,

"Encouraging the sharing of creative solutions and innovative practices which enable a shift in mindset necessary to drive change".

IN-HABIT will offer **sound evidence-based results** and **best practices** on the role of public spaces to boost IHW in European SMSCs.

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IN-HABIT's general expected KPIs are:

- IN-HABIT solutions replicated and EU and non-EU cities interested in replicating the project solutions
- Events where IN-HABIT results are presented
- Dissemination actions developed by the networks involved
- Awards and mentions obtained by IN-HABIT solutions

1.2 Communications objectives (COs) and key messages (KMs)

IN-HABIT solutions will be co-created with local stakeholders, mindset changes in categories at risk of exclusion/disadvantage will be boosted, new approaches to enhance inclusive health and wellbeing tested and results disseminated, social and technological solutions paired shifting the focus from smart, technology-driven cities to **human-centred cities** supported by the use of technology and infrastructures.

At a level of global and European institutional communication, key messages are:

- IN-HABIT contributes to creating innovative, affordable, and modular solutions that are viable examples of city transformation based on values and on the need to make public spaces inclusive, safer, greener and liveable under sustainable lifestyle practices.
- Sustainability in its different dimensions (social, environmental, economic, financial, technological, anthropic) is at the heart of the project.
- IN-HABIT solutions contribute to boost the cooperation among the local actors, showing out new frameworks and models to make common interests and goals achievable.

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- The solutions will be co-developed and implemented in the four cities and aim to explore various developing areas. In particular, the importance of co-design for urban regeneration projects.
- Communicate the use of European funding and in particular of H2020 projects.
- Communicate and share the multidisciplinary approach of the interventions.
- The involvement of Bogotá will extend the options to interact with the CELAC region.

In a local, cities and neighbourhood-related environment:

- Locally, the IN-HABIT project can mean a significant increase of visibility, especially in touristic areas. In addition, feeling part of a European and prestigious partnership.
- Local stakeholders that replicate the model of best practices in IHW proposed by the IN-HABIT project have a great opportunity to increase their own visibility and awareness raising capacity and options to act as ambassadors of sustainable practices in IHW.
- The rebuilt public spaces will be inspirational for many other areas in the world facing similar problems, in particular when addressing GDEI based co-design, co-deployment and co-management in different local conditions in four cities.
- Proposed visionary solutions will promote sustainable urban mobility patterns and sustainable physical and social connections among city areas, decrease spatial and social segregation and promote healthier diet and lifestyles, cultural life and livelihood opportunities in peripheral districts.

During the first two years, the main communication goals would be:

- to build IN-HABIT brand and awareness
- to make the brand recognisable
- to keep the communication accessible and focused on the research phases of the project
- to spread a clear meaning for each keyword shared

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- to create identification among cities
- to start engaging the most relevant stakeholders in a very effective way and help them in multiplying IN-HABIT communication and dissemination
- to start communicating at a local level in a very impactful and catchy way, trying different frameworks and tools to find out which works best in each of the four cities (information about the project in combination with local useful insights leading to education and good actions)
- to involve local community activators and observers in the very first digital campaign to increase awareness
- to reach out and connect to relevant external stakeholders, in particular those identified in § 1.3 and 1.4, to bring the project into the international debate and to foster shared solutions
- to enhance connections with relevant stakeholders at a local level, such as city networks, to strengthen relationships and capital investment opportunities in joint activities and events under coordination of the EC
- to strengthen the sense of Europe belonging and partnership and funding of the project through European funds.

Pillars of IN-HABIT communication:

- Focus on the solutions
- Stress accessibility
- Promote gender, diversity, equity and inclusive sensitive communication
- Be bridge-builders in each single communication action
- Dedicated storytelling for children and youth for each message
- Communicate the impact and change that projects have on people's lives, wellbeing and health
- Local stakeholders and beneficiaries can be targets and ambassadors at the same time, as targets may become partners and storyholders: the communication path is defined

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by asking what is expected from others and what they need to meet these and their own expectations, as well

- Stress the European dimension of the project

1.2.1 Starting the communication campaigns

The general communication campaign will start in M10, June 2021.

This choice takes into consideration the need of cities to organise the establishment of the IN-HUBs and of the project itself according to the time needed for each one. The first communication campaign, which will start from June 2021, will be a **general presentation campaign** for the project, through which all existing channels and a first press launch will be activated to propose the project to the public in a communication perspective at an international and institutional level.

Following this, it is expected that the four cities, once the IN-HUBs establishment has been set up, will be ready to take action for a **public presentation at a local level**, aimed at gathering the maximum visibility and consensus from local targets for the first time.

The activities carried out by the cities, which will have to include, in particular, a press launch, will always be coordinated by the communication coordinator (BOT for WP8), who will support the local staff also with dedicated operational training. The BOT team will make sure the local campaign, internal communication and campaigns of institutional communication of the project are convergent and consistent. It would be ideal for cities to start thinking about the communication actions they'd like to be implemented or they think would be more relevant from now to the month in which their own public presentation campaign is foreseen, considering to implement it between M13 and M18 (September 2021 and February 2022).

All the necessary information, any specific training for appointed key local contacts dedicated to communication in the cities, community activators and any other relevant actors to

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institutional communication (i.e., press officers being involved in the campaigns) and questions regarding operational activities can be discussed with the central coordinator of communication once the Stakeholder engagement strategy and activities run by WP5 are completed, planned from M6 onwards.

1.3 Project relevant actors – mapping and definitions

The IN-HABIT project is firmly based on direct involvement of people and collaboration as a way to achieve quality results. For this reason, **the idea that, in the project, depending on the situation and the action that involves it, any actor can be a sender/promoter or recipient, is a key starting point.**

A local association interested in actively supporting the project can be taken as an example: at the beginning it will be a target, since through the institutional communication the PPs will inform it, among other things, of the existence of the project, its aims, the modalities of participation. At a later stage, the same could be a communication vehicle to further targets and therefore, a sender, reporting the information acquired and participating in involving further groups. Along the way, it may also be a bearer of feedback that arises in its community to the PPs. In this sense the PPs will be a target for this association. Or it could ask the PPs to support its message (connected to IN-HABIT's visions) to its local communities (in this sense, the PPs will be a vehicle and endorser and the target will be the local groups connected to the association).

In short, where all-round proactivity of the subjects involved and multidirectional communication is expected, it should always be taken into consideration that each of the actors will be able, in various situations, to cover different roles.

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1.4 Who's Who in the project

In a classic definition, the stakeholder is any person interested in an initiative, be it more or less influential.

In the definition of project-level stakeholder, present in the Glossary to be integrated later on into this document and agreed by the PPs (led by Tesserae):

“the stakeholder is identified as any subject that has or may have an interest (a stake) in a project or programme. In disciplinary language, from business to policy it can assume different connotations. Stakeholders are often categorised through the acronym UGIP, representing four main categories: Users, Governance, Influencers, Providers. This scheme does not differ substantially from the quadruple helix social innovation model proposed in social sciences adopting civil society, government, academia and industry as the four essential agencies shaping social change (quintuple helix includes environment as the fifth factor).”

The stakeholder is not defined by a formal legal status or organisation: single individuals and informal coalitions are equally understood as legitimate stakeholders as long as they have established an interest or a relation with a given context. Within IN-HABIT, the meaning of the term captures the essential project's focus on inclusiveness. Accordingly, the process of stakeholder mapping and engagement is essentially dedicated to reaching out to the less represented and more at risk of discrimination and exclusion.

In this sense, the main project protagonists for communication and dissemination purposes are:

- **CORE - PROJECT PARTNERS** (organisations funded by the H2020 in this Project and taking part in the action)
- **GENERAL BENEFICIARIES** (people receiving direct or indirect benefits, such as the inhabitants in the four cities and the local groups that will benefit from the project in

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many ways, including the groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion - women, sexual minorities, children, youth ethnic minorities, migrants and refugees, disable people...)

- **LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS** (all the formal and informal subjects holding interests and potentially engaged in the actions of the project, in particular on the local field)
- **TARGET GROUPS** (groups targeted by the communication actions, such as community activators, decision makers, local networks, media stakeholders, etc.)
- **COMPREHENSIVE OR GENERAL STAKEHOLDERS** (grass-roots partners, decision makers, European groups representing specific interests, etc.)

Figure 1. IN-HABIT's project participants.

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The core project partnership of the IN-HABIT project is constituted by:

- **High-level RTD organisations (UCO, BSC, UNIPI, SUA, UREAD, PUJ):** specialised in social and technological aspects of urban management, health, culture, food, human interactions, art and environment, NBS, renewable energies, behaviour economics.
- **City Representatives (CORDOBA, RPR, LUCCA and NITRA)** are at the core of the project. Additionally, several more twin-cities have shown their interest in replicating outcomes. Their involvement ensures the embedding of the results in the city planning and their sustainability beyond the project. Some of these cities have a proven experience of working in international projects, while for others, IN-HABIT will be the first opportunity to participate in such initiatives. IN-HABIT will create an inclusive learning environment where skills will be transferred and capacities built, opening new avenues for participation to SMSCs in EU R&I actions.
- **Grass-root partners (AVUE, KQ, LCREA, HIDE)** fully embedded in the life of the neighbourhoods and cities where the VIS will be tested. Like the cities, some of these organisations have no previous experience of participation in EU projects. Partnering with more experienced partners will enhance their capabilities and increase the critical mass of actors involved in R&I actions at an EU level. AVUE and HIDE are civil society organisations, and KQ and LCREA are SMEs. KQ is an expert in food business development and LCREA in creative activities.
- **Other SMEs (TSR, BOT, B4B, LABORELEC, WTG)** with the necessary expertise to cover all the cross-cutting domains included in IN-HABIT. TSR is an expert in citizen engagement and urban social research and practice, BOT in citizen-science interactions, science dissemination and communication and storytelling, B4B in business incubation and coaching, LABORELEC & WTG in technological innovations. All of them have a long-standing track record of working in their field of expertise and broad experience of participation in international research projects.
- **Non-profit organisations (ISIM, DFC)** holding important know-how on H&W impact and mindset change. ISIM is an expert in impact monitoring and DFC in mindset change

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techniques by using its own Design Thinking based methodology to tackle challenges in an agile way.

- **General Beneficiaries:** inhabitants and residents of the four cities (multiple targets) especially collectives at risk of exclusion and discrimination, youth and children, all the EU and non-EU cities that could take advantage of the research and its results and the actors of the respective communities.

Figure 2. The IN-HABIT partnership.

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In addition to these, other relevant external stakeholders, the **comprehensive stakeholders**, must be considered:

- **EC (European Commission),**
- **sister projects,**
- **scientific societies,**
- **academia & research institutions,**
- **local and national and European policy makers,**
- **associations not directly involved,**
- **national stakeholders,**
- **schools, universities and educational authorities,**
- **local networks,**

bodies and authorities and all the other organisations that, learning about the IN-HABIT project, with different levels of involvement and proactivity, will follow it. Other relevant institutional actors are **social actors, movements, political parties, NGOs, civil society, local, national and supranational authorities.**

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Figure 3. Comprehensive stakeholder mapping.

A **stakeholder map** will be shared during the ongoing stakeholder mapping process to enable each local partner to share top tier stakeholder profiles to keep an eye on and any suggestions about possible groups to stay in touch with / to make aware about the project at the different stages of development.

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1.4.1 A dynamic identity

In a project like IN-HABIT, depending on the objectives and situations, a partner can become an ambassador, a beneficiary can become a storyholder, an external stakeholder can become an active part of the implementation of the initiatives, a target decision-maker can become an active constructor of messages concerning the project.

For this reason, when addressing the actors involved in the project, it is essential to take into consideration all the different roles they can play and how they lend themselves to achieving the objectives indicated above, making them aware of the possibility of passing from a stakeholder who receives value to an actor who actively transfers it to others and helps to create new ones.

Value-design strategic activities as a boost for the message positioning:

After mapping the main stakeholders, creating synergies with WP5 Stakeholders Mapping activities but also taking into account the specifics of the communication field, a **value map** will be built based on what each stakeholder could perceive as a main value in the project.

The value map will help with defining the message into the communication path and crafting an architecture of **value-based messages** to spread across all the audiences.

This activity of listening could be implemented as a peculiar and recurrent process to define and re-design the messages as the project moves forward.

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Guidelines for an active and planned involvement of new stakeholders:

Other relevant stakeholders that would take part in the project will be mapped and directly involved in the communication strategy through:

- asking them to report events and issues of importance to them (even to foresee some point of the editorial plan) and also to adapt the contents of the institutional communication by linking the topics to local topical issues that can involve more inhabitants and actors in the four cities;
- connecting to their social profiles and tagging/mentioning them while they publish relevant information;
- giving them the opportunity to propose initiatives aimed at deepening the themes of IN-HABIT or where these initiatives can give a boost to the project and research objectives;
- involving them in local activities where possible;
- organising their presence as IN-HABIT ambassadors **in a 'media narrative design' plan**, through which it will be defined how and when to make them storyholders and multipliers of the IN-HABIT project on the project's communication channels and their own profiles.

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2. IN-HABIT outreach channels by targets

The medium is the message, for this reason the medium selected for communication must **participate in conveying the message of inclusiveness and accessibility** and be **transversal** to the cohorts that can take part in the project in different ways, from children to young people to adults and seniors, in consideration of the most established media in each age group and across the various local cultures.

The experience is also determined by the characteristics of the channel as an incentive to use the information and advocational content. New channels to be co-defined with users as more appropriate to the context, such as podcast platforms, direct messaging, but also physical touchpoints can be taken into account.

Not only top-down and bottom-up communication channels will be privileged, but also **peer-to-peer communication** / recommendation ones: the communication unfolds on the channels also on the basis of the different purposes and levels of institutionality: for example, different social media channels might be used according to different purposes (Twitter for advocational, Facebook for activation, Instagram for campaigning and value based communication, LinkedIn for the return to stakeholders and on project life, YouTube for more immediate users' reporting from the cities' contexts).

The selection of channels at the local level also concerns the possibility of settling within local communication flows already functioning and activated by local organisations that daily inform citizens in a capillary way about activities and opportunities considered as **primary interest** (how to do a separate collection, how to access primary services offered by municipalities, such as accessing aid provided locally for disadvantaged groups). For this reason, part of the channels through which project communication passes must be defined on the basis of **ongoing collaborations** and the effective possibility of accessing these

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communication flows that are already widespread and considered of primary importance for citizens.

The identified local communication managers will be required to make a specific effort aimed at identifying the opportunities for access to these channels that are already tested at the local level and an initial analysis aimed at understanding their dynamics.

For this reason, **it is recommended that the PPs share their ideas** through the internal document which will be shared with all partners with the specific objective of **transferring local insights** to help with a better fine-tuning at a strategic level.

As a general disclaimer, target audiences in this project may be overlapping, but slightly different communication approaches are required and reported below.

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Table 1: IN-HABIT communication objectives per target audience.

Target	Communication objective	Message	Outreach channel	DECO Action
Decision-makers	Inform them about the project, support them in participating and explain how they can help with involving local actors, disseminate results and convince them about the replicability of the solutions	Decision-makers have a key role in changing the day-to-day life of citizens of small and medium size cities through new spaces, inclusion, wellbeing. As decision-makers, you can help the project established in your city to provide a huge impact and that will provide visibility and attractiveness to the cities, the administrators and the local actors.	Website Social media PR Leaflet Scientific publications Local events Stakeholder relations Direct communications-newsletters Meetings and conferences Papers and informative materials	Interaction via direct relations, dissemination activities, communication formats for public communication
EU Institutions	Provide information about the programme, involve, disseminate results, meet the achievements and share them among sister projects as well	Let them know that IN-HABIT is a useful and effective project with a huge attention to the EU value.	Website Social media PR Reports	Interaction via direct relations, deliverables, dissemination activities, communication formats for public communication. Participation in events and organisation of joint events and task forces
Local stakeholders	Inform, foster education, provide tools and arguments for outreach and dissemination, involve, help them in sharing local insights and feedback, help them to communicate in a clear, effective, gender neutral and inclusive way	Local stakeholders have a key role in making the project effective at a local level. You're part of a project that can be replicated in other cities around the world, providing a huge impact. Taking part in this project also means more visibility. Be	Website Social media Local Events PR Reports Papers and informative materials App Leaflet	Interaction via channel of external communication, direct relations, reports, dissemination activities, training and direct support day-to-day

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		a bridge builder and share your ideas and insights.	Multi format information WP8 leadership support: Training sessions Internal communication documents and guidelines	
Project partners (PPs)	Inform, foster education, provide tools and arguments for outreach and dissemination, involve, help them in sharing insights and feedback, help them to communicate in a clear, effective, gender neutral and inclusive way	The project partners have a key role in making the project effective at a local level. You're part of a project which can be replicated in other cities around the world, providing a huge impact. Taking part in this project also means more visibility. Be a bridge builder and share your ideas and valuable insights. WP8 leaders can help transform your idea into effective actions.	Website Social media Local events PR Reports Scientific publications App Leaflet Multi format information WP8 leadership support: Training sessions Internal communication documents and guidelines	Interaction via channel of internal communication, direct relations, reports, internal dissemination activities, training and direct support day-to-day
Universities, Scientific and Research community, Academia	Outreach and disseminate results	The project results are consistent and can be demonstrated, shared and replicated in other cities. Your interest in the research is welcomed and cooperation is encouraged.	Reports Scientific publications Papers PR Research insights in multiformat communication	Interaction via channel of external communication, direct relations, reports, internal dissemination activities, support in sharing the insights of the research. Scientific Conferences and Congress

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Sister and clustering projects	Share topics, arguments, best practices and opportunities to provide impact and involve stakeholders	IN-HABIT aims to cooperate with other projects which share values and will impact on the same topics.	Website Events Joint PR activities Social media (mentions, hashtags, tagging) Papers and informative materials Reports on the project results Recurrent meetings	Interaction via channel of external communication, direct relations, reports, dissemination activities, social media tagging and mentions, take part in third parties' events, joint actions
Inhabitants of the four cities	Involve, activate, make them storyholders and ambassadors, provide tools to create positive impact also after the end of the project	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city, bringing more opportunities in your day-to-day life. Get informed and involved and share information and opportunities to create a valuable impact in your city.	Website and local pages App Social media PR Leaflet and translated communications Papers and informative materials Local events Direct communications through newsletters or familiar channels provided by local third parties	Interaction via channel of external communication, direct relations, education, communication, outreach and dissemination activities, social media and app, Inform through the website
Categories at risk of exclusion / disadvantage or sensitive groups in the four cities	Inform, educate, involve, activate, make them storyholders and ambassadors, provide tools to create positive impact also after the end of the project, include	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city, bringing more opportunities in your day-to-day life. Get informed and involved and share information and opportunities	Website and local pages App Social media PR Leaflet and accessible communications Local events	Promoting the interaction based on the channel they are more familiar with, helping them interact with the digital environment, creating offline events if possible, stressing accessibility goals

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– general approach		to create a valuable impact in your city.	Direct communications through newsletters or familiar channels provided by local actors	
Categories at risk of exclusion for economic reasons	Inform, educate, involve, activate, make them storyholders and ambassadors, provide tools to create positive impact also after the end of the project, include, empower	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city, bringing more opportunities in your day-to-day life and empowering you, also with new prospects for inclusion in paths that can enhance you from a working point of view.	Direct contact via mobile or materials spread in local touchpoints Local events Direct communications through newsletters or familiar channels provided by local actors	Promoting the interaction based on the channel they are more familiar with, helping them interact with the digital environment, creating offline events if possible, stressing accessibility goals
Categories at risk of exclusion for social reasons (e.g., cultural minorities)	Inform, educate, involve, activate, make them storyholders and ambassadors, provide tools to create positive impact also after the end of the project, include, empower	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city, bringing more opportunities in your day-to-day and empowering you, also with new with prospects for inclusion in paths that can help you participate in public dialogue in a positive way and make your point of view and your needs known and to make them represented in public policies.	Leaflet translated and accessible communications Local events Website and local pages translated App Social media Direct communications through newsletters or familiar channels provided by local actors Direct contact via mobile or materials spread in local touchpoints	Promoting the interaction based on the channel they are more familiar with, helping them interact with the digital environment, creating offline events if possible, stressing accessibility goals

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Categories at risk of exclusion for reasons of gender	Inform, educate, involve, activate, make them storyholders and ambassadors, provide tools to create positive impact also after the end of the project, include, empower	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city, bringing more opportunities in your day-to-day life and empowering you, also with new with prospects for inclusion in paths that can help you participate in public dialogue in a positive way and make your point of view and your needs known and to make them represented in public policies.	Leaflet translated and accessible communications Local events Website and local pages translated App Social media Direct communications through newsletters or familiar channels provided by local actors Direct contact via mobile or materials spread in local touchpoints	Promoting the interaction based on the channel they are more familiar with, helping them interact with the digital environment, creating offline events if possible, stressing accessibility goals
Categories at risk of exclusion for reasons related to education	Inform, educate, involve, activate, make them storyholders and ambassadors, provide tools to create positive impact also after the end of the project, include, empower	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city, bringing more opportunities in your day-to-day life and empowering you, also with new prospects for inclusion in paths that can enhance your education and participation.	Leaflet and accessible communications Local events	Promoting the interaction based on the channel they are more familiar with, helping them interact with the digital environment where possible, creating offline events if possible, stressing accessibility goals
Grassroots partners and volunteers	Involve, activate, make them storyholders and ambassadors, provide tools to create positive impact also after the end of the project	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city, bringing more opportunities in your day-to-day life. Get informed and involved and share information and opportunities to create a valuable impact in your city.	Website Social media App Social media PR Leaflet Papers and informative materials Local events	Giving them all the necessary tools to multiply the message and involve other people and groups and sharing a part of the strategy to make them feel part of the IN-HABIT project and committed.

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			Direct communications through newsletters or familiar channels provided by local third parties	
Youth and Children	Educate, inform, involve, provide simple tools and ways to impact and share opinions and ideas	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city and more other cities and lives around the world, bringing more opportunities in people's day-to-day lives. Get informed and involved and share information and opportunities to create a valuable impact in your city.	Website and local pages App Social media PR Leaflet and accessible communications Local events Direct communications through newsletters or familiar channels provided by local actors	Promoting the interaction based on the channel they are more familiar with, helping them interact with each other through accessible and simple channels, giving them tools to multiply the messages sharing it with their families and friends
Schools	Give tools to involve and first-hand information about the project: they have a key role in multiplying and engaging local families	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city and more other cities and lives around the world, bringing more opportunities in families' day-to-day lives. This is a call for you to activate families in building a new way to live in the city in the next future.	Website and local pages App Social media PR Leaflet and accessible communications Local events Direct communications	Promoting the interaction based on the channel they are more familiar with, helping them interact with each other through accessible and simple channels, giving them tools to multiply the messages sharing it with other families
NGOs	Give tools to involve and first-hand information about the project: they have a key role in multiplying the message, engage and activate groups interested in	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city, bringing more opportunities in your day-to-day life. Get informed and involved and share information and opportunities to create a valuable impact in	Website Social media App Social media PR Leaflet Paper and informative materials	Giving them all the necessary tools to multiply the message and involve other people and groups and sharing a part of the strategy to make them feel part of IN-HABIT. Giving them all the information and paper

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	specific topics and support the institutional communication through their direct relations and presence in institutional contexts.	your city, support together the causes we both care about.	Leaflet and accessible communications to spread Local events Direct communications	they may use in an institutional context to link their storytelling with IN-HABIT
Other comprehensive stakeholders not mentioned above, such as local networks	Involve, activate, make them storyholders and ambassadors, provide tools to create positive impact also after the end of the project, activate them in involving groups we can't reach out to, ask for their help in learning to discover and understand local dynamics	Your ideas and actions count a lot and this project could change your city and other cities of the world. Get informed and involved and share information and opportunities to create a valuable impact in your city, support together the causes we both care about.	Website Social media App Social media PR Leaflet Paper and informative materials Leaflet and accessible communications to spread Local events Direct communications	Giving them all the necessary tools to multiply the message and involve other people and groups and sharing a part of the strategy to make them feel part of the IN-HABIT. Giving them all the information and paper they may use in an institutional context to link their storytelling with IN-HABIT

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2.1 General Overview – actions by targets

The WP8 leaders are determined to maximise the impact of each communication action that will be implemented, so that the messages related to the project can reach each target group in an appropriate manner. From the first conversations with the PPs based in the four cities, the WP8 leaders were able to learn how, in the different cities, there are completely inhomogeneous consumption habits of information and social interaction. For this reason, despite having identified macro groups of recipients in correspondence with the messages, in the coming weeks the framework will be enriched with the inputs generated by listening at the local level, which will be the starting point for defining how the key concepts of the project, expressed in the form of messages, can become contents defined not only on the basis of the priorities of topics and values expressed at a local level, but also on the basis of specific communication channels and tools that are more suitable for conveying these contents. The right to learn from the local contacts the real habits regarding the consumption of information and familiarity with communication tools for all local sub-segments, rather than defining a generalised and scarcely effective communication strategy, is therefore reserved.

A first forecast of actions that can be undertaken in correspondence with the various targets, and which may be subject to changes in the coming months, is presented below.

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Table 2: General Overview – actions by targets.

Target	Group	Channels	Tools
Decision makers	Local decision makers in charge	Website, social media, PR, leaflet, scientific publications, local events, stakeholder relations activities, direct communications – newsletters	Direct mailing and contacts, papers, press review, press releases, multiformat tools
	Global decision makers	Scientific publication, participation in events, website, social media, PR, stakeholder relations activities	Direct mailing and contacts, papers, press review, press releases
	Decision makers in cities not involved	Scientific publication, participation in events, website, social media, PR, stakeholder relations activities, app	Direct mailing and contacts, papers, press review, press releases, multiformat tools
	Inhabitants of cities not involved	Social media, website, online events, scientific publications, PR, dissemination of scientific results	Multiformat tools (videos, tutorials, podcasts, online meetings and events), press reviews, blog post
Institutional stakeholders	EU institutions	Deliverable, participating in events, scientific publications, PR, and also website and social media	Direct mailing and contacts, papers, press review, press releases
	EU associations	Participating in events, scientific publications, PR, and also website and social media, dissemination of results	Direct mailing and contacts, papers, press review, press releases

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	MEP/ EU and EP committees, shadow rapporteurs	Stakeholder relations and direct contacts, dissemination of the results, scientific publications, PR	Direct mailing and contacts, papers, press review, press releases
	Member states	Deliverable, participating in events, scientific publications, PR, and also website and social media	Direct mailing, papers and contacts, press review, press releases
Cities	Administrators	Website, social media, PR, leaflet, scientific publications, local events, stakeholder relations activities, direct communications – newsletters	Direct mailing and contacts, papers, press review, press releases, multiformat tools
	Inhabitants	Website, social media, PR, leaflet, scientific publications, local events, stakeholder relations activities, direct communications, newsletters, app	Leaflet, video, SMS , tutorial, podcasts, online meeting and events, games, social post, call to action and challenges
	Groups at risk of exclusion	Offline and online events, leaflet, social media, direct messaging, other channels and tools TBD relevant at local level, video	Leaflet, video, SMS, tutorial, podcasts, online meetings and events, games, social post, call to action and challenges, specifically targeted and tailored made
	Local Activators and Observers	Direct communication, social media, website, PR, leaflet and other tools relevant al local level, website	Multiformat tools (videos, tutorials, podcasts, online meetings and events)

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	Local Volunteers	Direct communication, multiformat information (videos, tutorials, podcasts, online meetings and events), social media, website, PR, leaflet and other tools relevant at local level	Multiformat tools (videos, tutorials, podcasts, online meetings and events) shared by social networks
	Grassroots partners	Direct mailing, website, social network	Leaflet, papers, infographics, but also multiformat tools (videos, tutorials, podcasts, online meetings and events)
	Youth and Children	Direct communication, multiformat information, social media, website, PR, leaflet and other tools relevant at local level, website	Leaflet, video, tutorial, podcasts, online meeting and events, games, social post, call to action and challenges
PPs	PPs	Website, social media, local events, PR, reports, informative publications, multi format information [WP8 leadership support training sessions, PR office support]	Direct mailing, shared folders, papers, meetings, leaflet, press release, press review
Universities and Scientific community		Reports, scientific publications, PR Research insights in multiformat, communication	Direct mailing, shared folders, papers, meetings, leaflet, press release, press review
Sister and clustering projects		Sharing events and experiences, joint press releases, social media, direct mailing, direct relations, website	Direct mailing, shared folders, papers, meetings, leaflet, press release, press review

Table 2: General Overview – actions by targets

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However, given D 8.1. is submitted at the end of this month while the Dissemination and Communication Plan a living document, an **addendum starting from M6-M8 is planned, in order to include relevant specifications for local neighbourhoods and contexts** which might arise from the training activities and local stakeholder mapping to be implemented with partner TSR and others in WP5. This addendum will be duly updated and report checklists and guidelines for local communication.

At the same time, the Gender & Diversity Toolkit and Glossary, which share different timelines than the DC plan, will be integrated in the upcoming months upon their completion.

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2.2 Personality, Tone of Voice and Language

Clear, easy-to-use communication guidelines for the main channels and targets are provided in Annex 2 to this document – Communication Guidelines (ref. D 8.1).

Communication and Engagement Actions and Tools (Task 8.2)

Dissemination Actions and Tools (Task 8.3)

Replication, Upscaling and Dissemination communication frameworks will be used to target different groups: inhabitants, children and youths, decision makers at international levels, global NGOs, representatives of international groups of interests, global networks and European institutions and many other cited and mapped in §1.3 and 1.4 (global outreach). Solutions will be co-deployed and co-managed through a multi-actor approach and a multi-disciplinary community connecting Academia, Research Organisations, SMEs, Private for Profit, NGOs, Development Agencies, Public Authorities, Citizen groups/local Communities and Media from different EU and non-EU countries. Dissemination will take place using a combination of different targets, timelines and strategies. In the first two years of the project the focus will be on informing people about IN-HABIT's work, from year three to five dissemination will concentrate on engaging people in the work, and in year five and beyond attention will be turned to upscaling/replicating the work.

Over the five years, tasks will include: launching a **communication campaign** in each city to support the establishment of the IN-HUBS; organising both a **training session on storytelling**, blogging and communication, **data storytelling** and impact communication, and meetings for the selected community activators; creating a **website** to house the projects; developing a mobile app **INHABIT-APP**; building games; teaching children how to write stories inspired by their neighbourhood and city; and creating four **live videos** to document the work undertaken in each of the four cities.

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IN-HABIT's **brand personality** is that dimension of the project identity that arises when certain attributes and human personality traits are associated with it.

This project is aimed first of all at the people and has as its objective that of the evolution to be bridge-builders and present the brand in its **human dimension** to every possible interlocutor, enhancing those characteristics that favour an **open and rich exchange** in the name of inclusion, collaboration, understanding and sincerity.

2.2.1 IN-HABIT – personality traits

If the IN-HABIT project were a person it would be ...

balanced, honest, open-minded, inclusive, equitable, an explorer, aware, curious, an insider, engaging, professional, determined.

The tone of voice in common institutional communications:

It should be: mid-formal, respectful, empathetic, aware, thoughtful, passionate, enthusiastic, colloquial, advocate (where needed), scientific (in dissemination).

It should never be: too self-celebratory (admitted to celebrate the good results of IN-HABIT and the sister and clustering projects), ideological.

The tone of voice in local communication:

It should be: enthusiastic, cheerful, colloquial, engaging, direct, reflective, questioning, reassuring, scientific (in dissemination).

It should never be: disinterested, aggressive, indifferent, detached, dominant, ideological.

The tone of voice in stakeholder and media relations:

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It should be: attentive, informative, direct, reassuring, open, expert, scientific (only for dissemination).

It should never be: too solemn, too informal, insecure, ambiguous, wavering, too direct, a “big mouth”.

The tone of voice in communication with young people and children:

It should be: colloquial, interested, close, open to listening, reassuring, enthusiastic, energetic.

It should never be: ideological, confused, abrupt, obnoxious, disappointed, sceptical, offended, impatient, condescending, blunt or rough.

The tone of voice in communication with collectives at risk of exclusion / disadvantage

It should be: neutral, colloquial, thoughtful, direct, reassuring, open minded, encouraging.

It should never be: abrupt, aggressive, indifferent, aloof, condescending, dominant, cynical, derogatory, desperate, hostile, impatient, aggressive, bored, sarcastic, melancholic, sceptical, impertinent.

Across all the communication, the language should be: clear, simple and concise, unique, informal, inclusive, educational, no technicalities, explain acronyms, not traceable to political and social connotations (neutral).

Locally: bilingual/multilingual

2.3 Website

The IN-HABIT website (Task 8.2 Communication and engagement actions and tools, D8.3) was created with the dual mission of **informing and including** and is designed to ensure accessibility to the project and its protagonists and to make cities and their evolutionary process protagonists.

In order to develop a strategy that follows the progress of the step-by-step process, it is expected that the site will be taken from a simple landing page to a sharing platform in 2021,

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through three main releases, co-defined with the relevant PPs. The first release has been shared during the PP meeting in January 2021 and will continue as a co-design activity throughout M6/M7. Two following releases will be implemented.

2.3.1 First release, M6/M7 (Feb/March 2021)

By February 2021, the website will contain:

- a more complete home page
- a section for cities' updates
- events and project updates
- contact page (updated)
- reserved areas that will contain tools for local facilitators and activators will be projected.

2.3.2 Second Release, M8-10 (Apr-Jun 2021)

Between April and June 2021, the following elements will be added:

- More organised contents, particularly referring to cities but also to the local neighbourhoods that will be involved in the project and their experiences
- Upload of milestone timeline and relevant infographics on the homepage and on the "About" page
- Special pages dedicated to the cities, where local communication managers can update everything interesting about local topics. Specific content would be in the local language, thus allowing accessibility
- Upcoming events and related resources (might be a calendar)
- Completion of the PP profiles
- A new way to consult the press review, more effective for press use
- Enhanced social media feeds

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2.3.3 Third Release, M16 (end of 2021)

By the end of the year, the following elements will have been added:

- The resources section for cooperation and synergies with partners
- Fully-working Reserved Area – basically containing tools for partners and facilitators
- Upgrade of the Media page (not only press releases, but multimedia content when available from locals) depending on the strategy and channels co-defined
- Special section (or redirect) for children and schools (TBD)
- A place for local grassroots initiatives (TBD)

Figure 3. Timeline of website releases (2-3).

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2.4 App

The **INHABIT-APP** (D8.6, D8.8) will provide access to **innovative behavioural games and activities** as developed by WP6 and WP7; it will be **geolocalized** in the cities involved in the project, with a flexible and upgradeable architecture. A first version will be delivered in M12 and then tested in each city until final delivery in M36.

The app will be extremely simple and therefore innovative in its ease of use: it's like a **friendly fellow citizen**. The app will geolocate the users, entrust them with a role (tourist, citizen, young explorer, administrator), and at this point communicate the following with them (PUSH notifications):

- a) content by spatial proximity (you're close to something that interests you and maybe you're not aware of it), or conveyed by QR codes dotted around the city (photograph and receive);
- b) content by temporal proximity (an event next week, a discount for something useful);
- c) communications about activities, discounts, offers you're entitled to.

On the other hand, it allows the user to communicate requests, report disservices etc. directly to the city administrations (PULL), and respond to surveys and/or behavioural games whose results, and data (movement, activities, reading, consultations) on citizens' use of the city, are delivered – in an anonymous form – to the administrators. It will be integrated with the IN-HABIT website.

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2.5 Virtual environment

The virtual environment of the project is affected by the **habits of use** and access to different channels at different times of the day and in the lives of citizens.

Local communicators, then, will have to be proactive in bringing the institutional communication of the project onto those channels used and disseminated at the local level, taking into consideration the **different local targets** that may not all have the same interest or access to certain channels.

Consideration of the virtual context in which engagement can take place must be **holistic** and start from questions such as:

- What are the means that the different targets of the local community use to socialise? (Chat? Direct messaging?)
- Which ones do they entertain through? (TV Series? YouTube? Podcasts?)
- Through which channels do they collect useful information to carry out work achievements or achievements related to their home life?
- What means do the public administration and local authorities use to make mandatory services accessible or that they want to extend to citizens?

These questions will be a starting point for the training work carried out with local communicators and local observers and will serve as a baseline for the local specific addendum to communication guidelines to be put in place once the training has been completed. Besides, modular sessions of FAQ will be guaranteed for key contacts and local communicators and observers to be carried out on dissemination and communication matters at local level.

This material will be available in a communication toolkit for internal usage for the local stakeholders and everyone participating in the project, including relevant guidelines and materials for communication.

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What tools do local public and private bodies dealing with social services, justice, transport, etc. use to communicate with their audiences?

Local digital channels, then, can be the preferred place for **grassroots initiatives** and host specific social media campaigns to find local volunteers.

In any case, **all the channels used must be mapped in a synoptic representation to be updated on a recurring basis**, so that the WP8 leaders will be aware of all the channels in use, which should be monitored and from which it is possible to collect useful insights.

2.6 Offline environment

Offline communication activities (events, conferences, travel, meetings, meetings with stakeholders) will, for the first year, be carried out **in compliance with local restrictions** due to the regulations issued for the pandemic emergency.

All communication opportunities will be **designed in their online version** wherever feasible in order not to generate efforts to design non-viable offline initiatives.

Printed materials, overview:

The dissemination of paper materials (**leaflets**) is expected for the **whole first year** of the project, 2021, to support the communication that local partners will be able to make of the project with local targets.

Similarly, for the months of the project in which the pandemic is expected to have been overcome, the design and construction of:

- A first **printed leaflet** for each city will be crafted to share the general pillars of the project.

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- A **more complete leaflet**, even translated in the local languages and containing additional information about how the project impacts locally will follow to support general campaigning (late 2021).

Annex 1 to this document is the Visual Identity manual on the basis of which all materials, online and offline, will be designed and created (ref. D8.1).

2.7 Social Media strategy

It is essential that the social media strategy is planned on two levels: institutional and local, the latter with the collaboration of PPs.

At an institutional level, the use of social media profiles would boost the IN-HABIT project awareness, helping to manage the brand reputation as well as the communication of the central messages:

- The **power of transnational cooperation** in a European consortium makes IN-HABIT a project that can definitely give relevant results.
- The **involvement of scientific excellence** and partners aware of local issues is the main way to contribute in solving societal challenges which can impact people's everyday lives and give relevant results to policymakers as well as to the scientific community.
- The society will benefit from **research** even outside the cities involved.

Main objectives of the institutional communication will be:

- a. to disseminate results,
- b. to make the institutional stakeholders and media aware,
- c. to encourage big partnerships,
- d. to inform multiple audiences,

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- e. to push the multiplier effect,
- f. to engage with opinion leaders and encourage informed discussions in peer-to-peer groups (like professional organisations, policy-makers...)

At the local level, the social media strategy would:

- help recruit volunteers;
- engage with local audiences and partners;
- build local networks of people who can debate and act on relevant global issues (e.g., through peer-to-peer groups) and give positive influence to decision-makers and local industries, also proposing new approaches to public and private local challenges;
- build networks to find new researchers ready to help;
- explain to the local community how they can benefit from the project and the research;
- carry out crowdfunding research;
- recruit local partners who will give continuity to the values of the project even outside and after its end;
- give strength and space to grassroots initiatives led with the support of the local activators.
- monitor conversations, to understand and analyse the citizen sentiment.

Periodic updates on this progress will be included in the corresponding dedicated local newsletters.

Social media profiles are also central to enforcing the **dissemination**, in particular:

- by covering the results as soon as they're available;
- by reporting and sharing information about workshops and events;
- by reaching out to specialist audiences – peer-to-peer groups such as professional organisations, policy-makers, vertical industries, etc.;

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- by making people aware about the results of the research and enabling them to take-up and use the results.

Regarding the **outreach activities**, social media is foreseen as one of the **main communication assets** in communication with targets such as youth, schools and children, who are often more familiar with the social media environment, and will thus be explored in the dedicated activities to be planned from 2022 on.

2.8 A quick Q&A on the Social Media strategy

WHERE is the IN-HABIT project on social media?

It is currently on Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter and will soon be on Instagram and YouTube. More channels could be added, especially for local use, when training of community activators and evaluations on the effectiveness of social media in a local context have been carried out.

WHO will be in charge of social media for the consortium?

BOT is in charge of the strategy and the local appointed people to drive the local strategy and to give feedback on the impact at the social level where the consortium is not completely enabled to understand social dynamics because of the linguistic gap and the lack of awareness on the main environmental issues. Local appointed people (community activators and key local contacts), after completing the communication training, will be able and empowered to follow the local communication activities themselves with BOT's support, where needed.

WHO is the target audience?

For the institutional communication strategy: institutions, associations, scientific community, media, sister and clustering projects, political groups, decision-makers, groups of interest, think tanks, at a global, European and local level. This communication seeking a more global outreach will be in English.

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At a local level: groups of citizens, associations, families, categories at risk of exclusion/ disadvantage, sensitive collectives, local companies, universities and researchers, youth, schools and children, everyone involved in creating a relevant social impact.

Moreover, at a local level, the communication will be in both English and the local language.

HOW will an effective and engaging communication framework be implemented?

- Through real-time communication on global topics which are relevant for the IN-HABIT project.
- Through an advocational tone of voice where activism is communicated at the same time, especially locally.
- Through a very basic and clear communication on how to face everyday life and issues with a new mindset.
- Communicating the impact of the project on people's lives will be one of the primary focuses.

English will be the main language used on social media. According to the needs and preferences of each partner, local languages can also be used to reach specific target audiences.

WHAT content should be shared?

Currently the content is scheduled and planned every two weeks, starting from a general plan in which a couple of month-long macro-campaigns are planned. Over the coming months, a strategy which can bring together the institutional communication strategy and the local one is expected to be co-defined with the help of the local communication managers.

WHEN?

Content will be posted two to four times a week on the project accounts (institutional communication) and an additional one or two localised posts for each city are expected. The mix of argumentation would vary depending on the phase of the project.

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2.8.1 IN-HABIT social profiles

To learn more about the project and find out how to get involved, all the targets can visit the IN-HABIT website: inhabit-h2020.eu

or they may connect on social media:

FB: @inhabith2020

T: @INHABIT_H2020

LI: [linkedin.com/company/inhabit-h2020](https://www.linkedin.com/company/inhabit-h2020)

2.9 Next steps in social media strategy: from goals to contents

In the phase in which the project is not yet publicly presented and the design and research work of local contacts is ongoing, the social campaign includes these micro-objectives, as follows as an example. They will be expanded and further explored on a more structured social media plan and calendar as the project develops.

Table 3: IN-HABIT communication from goals to contents.

Main objectives	Content type
Spread vision	What IN-HABIT is
Partners warm up	Who IN-HABIT storyholders are
Inform/educate	Why IN-HABIT
Make it accessible	How to live the IN-HABIT experience
Bound topics X target	Who IN-HABIT is referring to/talking to
Localisation of the project	Where IN-HABIT lives
Local topic ownership	How IN-HABIT plays its strengths locally
Unique communicative path	Glossary + "What's this hashtag"

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Disambiguate and create a common starting point	FAQs
Engage and make feel people involved	What to do to share the message
Make authoritative	Who speaks about it
Define the context	What's going on around IN-HABIT (Prioritise EU)
Draw a line	What's done and next actions to carry out
Get in action	Presenting 2021 action plan
Make dream	Presenting projections of "possible cities of the future"
Celebrate together	Celebrate Christmas, New Year

Table 3: IN-HABIT communication from goals to contents.

Use of common glossary and hashtags through the social profiles:

The use of **common words** is a key practice of IN-HABIT's DECO strategy because it contributes to achieving the goal of **creating a shared code** with all stakeholders and beneficiaries of the project since its inception. With the support of Tesseract (TSR) and the corresponding PPs working on a glossary that is also useful for the project in a more holistic sense, **keywords** will be identified that can become relevant for communication on social profiles and that are also significant on the basis of the most recent trending topics on the social networks used, which in the initial phase will be Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter.

Hashtags will be used to:

- increase outreach and join topic-specific conversations;
- capitalise on existing trends (find emerging hashtags to boost the research with the right audiences);
- group content and help people who are taking part in a specific event to find related posts and discussions on a specific topic;
- bring new opinions into a discussion about specific topics.

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A basket of hashtags is being defined and one hashtag a week is being published to explain their meanings and how they should be used to bring an opinion into a conversation or to find a discussion on a specific conversation.

At the same time, **the Glossary** will be used with the aim of making the meaning of each word unique and shared. Posts are already being shared in which specific words are introduced to the social community, who are asked to share with their followers and contact anyone who can contribute to the discussion and who could be interested in taking part in the project due to an existing interest in the topic or being active at a local level in a social challenge where the topic is relevant.

This would be exceedingly helpful in identifying and building **a quality audience**, exploiting the power of the project's online followers to multiply the message within the communities they belong to. Also, it would be part of the Gender and Diversity perspective toolkit (D5.1) feeding the plan.

How to use social posting to involve others:

- Through the daily monitoring of the social media audience's conversations
- Retweeting to engage with audiences
- Reposting on relevant topics and issues, adding a caption to explain the project's specific interest
- Starting online discussions e.g., by asking opinions or questions
- Replying to messages within a couple of hours if possible
- Planning social posts but, at the same time, not forgetting to monitor trending hashtags
- Identifying and selecting interesting opinion leaders to follow, with the hope of a follow back
- Tagging project partners
- Using @EU_H2020 and #H2020 in every tweet to maximise their visibility

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How to always be on point:

The communication would always be aligned to the topics debated by the public opinion on a large scale. To always be on point, a **specific calendar** with all the relevant recurrent annual events powered by the main institutions is being crafted, and this is where the relevant events pointed out by sisters and clustering projects partners and all the relevant occurrences and anniversaries concerning the project topics (also pointed out by the project partners, who would also be supposed to share the upcoming local events with BOT) will be added.

The **editorial plan** will be split into five files (one for the institutional communication level and one file for each city, which can be used to plan the local communication), which will be shared with the local communication managers. The editorial plan will contain a **complete calendar of international days** and will help them to find out how to share the project's messages at a local level and transfer IN-HABIT's messages and values into the local public debate.

2.9.1 How to use social networks in a safe and profitable way

The general rules for **safe and profitable communication** on social networks provide for some practices that local communication managers will be called to align with. In particular, IN-HABIT's communication on social profiles must reflect the requirements of clarity, transparency, accessibility, timeliness, neutrality, brevity.

For this reason, within the posts:

- technical terms must be limited and acronyms explained;
- posts cannot contain more than three sentences;
- the posts must be short but exhaustive, the references to other posts or organisations must be contextualised;
- the selected contents and formats must take into account the values of the project (in particular inclusion);

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- communications must have a neutral tone appropriate to the institutional context in which the project develops, avoiding excessive hype or any form of implicit judgement and reference to clichés and explicit on facts, circumstances, places, people. The contents must always be harmless and prepared in respect of the different cultures and the possible sensitivities of the reference audiences;
- emotions can be expressed, maintaining a mid-formal tone of voice, especially if they concern the achievement of IN-HABIT objectives (e.g., enthusiasm for the achievement of a goal or for the result of some research);
- the contents must contain references to sources and resources, both for the recognition of credits and to allow the readers to further explore the topics and make them their own. Likewise, in the creation of post contents, links to relevant events, sites and initiatives will always be taken into consideration;
- the contents must be mainly in English on the institutional profiles of IN-HABIT and may also be in the relevant local language in the profiles linked to activities promoted by local partners;
- when referring to external sources, it will always be preferable to select institutional or recognised sources;
- the contents of the social networks will not be able to refer to insights from the IN-HABIT project or other projects that are not yet public or final;
- the information conveyed by the posts must be accurate and verified, to strengthen the credibility of the source over time;
- the sharing on social profiles of public news and articles that have appeared in the press must be timely, in order to encourage the media that want to talk about the project to always refer to the institutional channels first (website, social profiles, etc.);
- it is advisable to vary the content of the posts by experimenting with the use of various formats. Posts containing videos, images and photos must be designed starting from the official visual identity to ensure consistency and recognition of the source, as well as being attractive. Videos must always be subtitled in English;

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- the results of the research and the milestones achieved that are published on social networks can also be made public through ad hoc presentations, data storytelling, presence at events, press launches;
- finally, particular attention must be paid to the accuracy of the translations both in form and substance.

2.9.2 Guidelines on posting priorities: when to post

The communication of IN-HABIT must be **timely**, especially with regards to the publication on social profiles.

In planning content, publication priority must be given, in order, to:

- ongoing events relevant to IN-HABIT, imminent and of high strategic and communicative value, particularly newsworthy and current;
- results achieved and relevant activities of the project partners and consortium members;
- press review on the project.

2.9.3 Timetable for an effective campaigning approach

To ensure the visibility of the initiatives and events promoted, each initiative relevant to the IN-HABIT project must involve the communication team to allow timely planning of pre-, during and post-event promotion activities on social media (as well as in multi-channel communication).

For this reason, any activity for which communication is necessary must be communicated to the communication coordinator (WP8/BOT) at least six weeks before the date of the event. In the following weeks:

- The contents must be defined, the participants and guests / speakers, the languages in which the communication must be translated, the coordinated image must be designed

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and created (which must also be adapted to the social formats deemed necessary), and the keywords and reference hashtags, which will be inserted in the posts from the first communication on the matter. In the case of initiatives that involve the construction of an event page on social media, this must be done before the publication of the first promotional post.

- During the events, in case of live-tweeting, a list of approved tweets must be defined in advance. In case of live-posting, a list of approved posts must be defined in advance.
- In the follow-up of the event, it is advisable to continue to use the hashtag in the posts relevant to the topics of the event, also taking up initiatives promoted by third parties.
- In case of communication of events promoted by the EC or by other EU online platforms, remember to use all channels, hashtags and means made available by institutional partners to ensure maximum visibility.

2.10 Traditional Media & Press

Media outreach and communication is essential to **broaden the audience** of the project and make it known to stakeholders on a large scale.

Communication through the press, radio and TV has a local connotation, for this reason the press office activities will be led by a central press office coordinated by WP8/BOT that will coordinate the work for four other appointed key contacts and dedicated people supporting BOT during the project lifetime located in the four cities whose contribution will be empowered by the support of local press offices and official channels and spokespeople where available. Each of them will have the task of collecting the requests of the local media and processing them according to the rules of this DECO strategy, coordinating with the central press office when deemed useful and at the same time being called to be proactive towards the local and national press, to ensure maximum visibility of the project. The local contacts will also be responsible for collecting local press reviews, identifying and reporting on relevant local facts that are particularly interesting for project communication (or making the project

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more communicable at local level), monitoring local events and agendas, local publications, the translation of press releases into the local language. A local contact has been appointed for translation of material of interest into local language as well. Local key contacts and support personnel are recommended to use media contact lists in accordance with current rules on privacy and data processing.

From M6, February 2021, an internal folder will be co-built and shared with the PPs and key contacts in the cities. During the following months it will be updated, containing:

- accurate and updated information and contacts on the PPs;
- a background document that summarises the project, values, participants, milestones;
- the profiles of official and local spokespersons;
- a database of authorised photos (of people, places, events), of images and of videos and frames free of copyright that can be shared with the press.

Researchers and technical partners will always be consulted and involved in interviews where their know-how and role can guarantee quality and credibility in communication.

To facilitate press review operations and have complete reports on the performance of Media PR activities, monitoring activities will be taken into consideration. The press releases, in the various phases (outreach, launch and follow-ups), will be coordinated by the central press office at least one month in advance of each launch. The communication materials will be adjusted from time to time to give the press concise and profiled contents on the needs of each reporter.

The press launch of the project presentation is scheduled for June 2021.

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2.11 Newsletter

The newsletter is a direct means of communication with the targets that must be optimised to give a **targeted and interesting communication** to each target, bringing together the relevant highlights, useful and practical information.

Different kinds of communications are taken into consideration, and it is suggested to design:

- A **general newsletter** aimed at a large recipient of stakeholders and citizens, who will be able to subscribe through the site, that will highlight project highlights, press reviews discussing the project, interesting articles from the network, recurring content also if available from local communicators in catchy formats (podcasts, videos, reportage) and information useful to the target audience.

This newsletter might have special issues dedicated to dissemination and communication of the project results, always addressed to a wide recipient of stakeholders and citizens interested in and involved in the project.

The general newsletter might have issues specifically dedicated to project partners that will contain the most relevant highlights, press reviews, reports on the progress of the project and the results achieved, such as an **internal newsletter**.

Expected frequency: every three months.

- A **local newsletter** connected to the news and useful information that each local communication coordinator will be able to build starting from local projects. It will be in the local language and will merge information on the project such as local events and useful information at the local level, which will make it interesting and attractive. It would be a more internal newsletter for local stakeholders and facilitators who support the activities necessary to carry out the project. It will be implemented by the local communicators and observers with the support of key contacts, trained by BOT.

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Expected frequency: to be defined with local stakeholders and key contacts, recommended: every two months once the activities in the IN-HUBS reach capacity.

All the newsletters will include a final section with a **call to action** where the various ways to participate and support the project will be indicated to the different targets according to the options identified for each (from sharing to local activation methods).

2.12 Workshops and Events

Workshops and events are a central part of the IN-HABIT project because they allow the **sharing of tools and knowledge** with the bearers of the project's messages and objectives. The planned events are, to date, the following, still to be confirmed due to the current health situation:

- Seven consortium meetings: kick-off, five annual meetings and one final meeting
- Three dissemination events that each partner will select according to its expertise (scientific conferences, urban-related conferences, technical conferences or meetings, etc.) and in order to maximise IN-HABIT dissemination options
- One training event to train community activators per city in all IN-HABIT methodologies at the beginning of the project.
- One cross-case visit of six representatives per city to the other cities
- One visit to Bogota of three representatives of each of the EU cities
- Three exploitation meetings to gather the most promising entrepreneurs from each year business call
- Three mindset change workshops in each city with educators
- One training the trainers workshop
- Travel of technological partners to ensure and check the deployment of sensors and devices in the pilot cities

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- Travel of partners in charge of monitoring the four cities to supervise and train the local teams

Other training actions have to do with the sharing of brief **“how to” guides** to spread the project communication guidelines in an easy-to-use, user-friendly way to PPs and community users. This is thought in particular to create **digital contents** corresponding to the contents and deposited on the website, in particular for WP8 communication actions and youth and children labs and training sessions, to **ensure accessibility** to the basic tools and effectiveness and **continuity of the training process** even if the workshop sessions are over and the need arises to extend this training to new figures in support of the project, or if new organisations join the project and are willing to support activators in their tasks, for which training may be necessary.

2.12.1 Training second life: sharing tools for local inclusion

The training in WP8 will not only give notions, but will enable the use of some tools **in practice**, in particular the digital ones connected to the aims of the project.

Some training contents, therefore, can be designed to have a *“second life use case”*: at the local level some material can be reused by organisations which, by taking on targeted training activities, can extend them to categories of citizens that they aim to include and which are currently excluded because they lack the know-how and tools necessary to interact with their community (also due to the digital gap).

The training documentation, then, can be designed from the initial stages to also have the purpose of **providing a means of inclusion** to those who, at the local level, want to give voice to the project and at the same time use the project's skills as a means of inclusion and involvement of specific targets.

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2.13 Communication formats and multimedia

Effective communication also depends on the choice of formats that can boost the objectives of informing, creating clear reports on the results achieved, engaging, involving and bringing project communication in an **accessible and usable way** into the daily life of the target communities.

The selection of formats is even more important in a pandemic scenario.

For this reason, the formats to be preferred for communication and dissemination on the various channels will be:

- Short video
- Infographics and data visualisation
- Infotainment or edutainment podcast

Training on these specific formats will be made available for community activators and appointed people (youths in particular) to provide **interesting, engaging content** consistent with the project guidelines.

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2.14 Networking with other projects

2.14.1 Clustering activities with sister projects

The DECO Plan also foresees **clustering activities** to support close cooperation and joint dissemination strategies with other EU projects tackling similar issues. Periodic bilateral exchange of news and results, joint presence in events and the collaborative approach will **foster knowledge exchange**, synergy creation, new partnerships and future projects aimed to develop IHW and sustainable urban development approaches.

The IN-HABIT project will undertake joint activities with sister and clustering projects – those involved in the same *H2020 EU call on Visionary and integrated solutions to improve well-being and health in cities (SC5-14-2019)* in the *H2020-EU.3.5.2. - Protection of the environment, sustainable management of natural resources, water, biodiversity and ecosystems* programme.

VARCITIES	<p>The project aims to create a vision for future cities with the citizens and the so-called human community at the centre, implementing innovative ideas and adding value by creating sustainable models for improving the health and well-being of citizens facing diverse climatic conditions and challenges around Europe. Public spaces are envisioned as people-centred areas that support creativity, inclusivity, health, and happiness for the citizens.</p>
GOGREEN ROUTES	<p>It creates a unique approach to nature-based solutions by creating green corridors and cultivating a positive human-nature relationship. The project's goal is to position European citizens as world ambassadors of urban sustainability.</p> <p>Advancing mental health and well-being, nature-based enterprise, sustainable physical activity, and digital, cultural and knowledge innovation raise awareness about links between human and environmental health.</p>
EUPOLIS	<p>The project will deploy natural systems to enhance public health and well-being and create resilient urban ecosystems, design a structured approach that integrates existing natural and</p>

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	engineered urban systems and define their joint social, cultural and economic effects to regenerate and rehabilitate urban ecosystems to create inclusive and accessible urban spaces.
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Networking and joint communication with other sister projects that share IN-HABIT values and objectives supports the IN-HABIT project to:

- reach new indirect audiences;
- increase its awareness towards communities sensitive to the topics covered;
- increase the multiplier effect;
- support the dissemination and adoption of research results, making them useful to new stakeholders;
- capture ideas from other projects and joint communication opportunities;
- know best practices to make the project relevant in daily life;
- try to figure out where other projects are most impactful and support them in finding relations with IN-HABIT local activities;
- make the social media plan on point: others’ relevant events need to be considered while the project’s campaigning loop is planned.

The touchpoints and networking moments are:

- Social media through tagging, mentions, in reference to events
- Participation in events of European and global significance
- Opportunities for direct relationships aimed at cooperation on project objectives
- Events and training sessions, trips to cities and to Bogotá

For networking to be effective, it is necessary that the contacts and opportunities that emerge are always **updated in the stakeholder map** and deepened according to a method for defining the priorities for the different interlocutions and the responsibilities of managing the various relationships, which are defined according to the opportunities they aim for and the know-how required to bring the best onboard.

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Each new relationship must therefore ideally be included in the stakeholder map with a note relating to the area of potential interest.

At the same time, **training sessions** will always include a special mention on how to create a continuous and effective follow up with new stakeholders.

In particular, WP8 suggestions and proposals for clustering activities with sister projects include:

Proposals for communication and joint actions on strengthening dissemination and outreach actions:

- Coordinate with other clustering projects communication WPLs to share a common strategy towards a global outreach at a European level, especially regarding topics involving EU policies and currently debatable topics (i.e., inclusion, well-being, ageing, etc.)
- Coordinate with other clustering projects communication WPLs on a regular basis (joint operational Task Force on communication and dissemination) to share common knowledge about:
 - best practices in general and institutional communication
 - best practices in local communication and storytelling
 - facing common challenges and how to overcome them (digital divide, COVID - 19 impact, engagement of citizens and vulnerable groups, children and youths, inclusiveness, etc.)
 - developing a common toolbox and engaging multipliers (online and social media communication, coordinated)
 - exploitation of project outcomes

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- Work together on a common agenda to share with EASME and other significant authorities
- Collating resources: e.g., educational content, media libraries, training and educational resources pages, gathering of examples on NBS or cultural innovation etc.
- Create comprehensive, cross-sectional content along the projects to enhance understanding of their purpose beyond the project at a greater level: infographics, data sheets, “killer facts”. Underline policy relevance in communications as well
- Work with fellow clustering projects on a common glossary to build a strong, clear identity for dissemination purposes across targets
- Joint activities/events, both online and offline, for amplification:
 - share projects’ internal calendars
 - create a common calendar of events at an EU level
 - track relevant events and initiatives and invite relevant stakeholders/speakers, starting from sister projects sharing their experiences
 - organise workshop meetings on common grounds (i.e., storytelling in your neighbourhood)
- Use existing connections and networks
 - for global outreach and international cooperation
 - to broaden impact on social media and online communities
- Collaborate on a common strategy for the engagement of groups at risk of discrimination
- Propose a joint conclusive output telling history and impact of the projects (perhaps through a short video)

Shared events can be found in § 4.

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2.15 Local to global communication

The aim is to bring IN-HABIT topics into the **everyday public dialogue**, creating a link between local issues and ideas which are suitable to be extended on a global level – such as inspiring solutions for other cities' inhabitants.

The challenges proposed by the IN-HABIT project want to be an example of how collaboration is the engine of the evolution of cities towards the future and the improvement of the quality of life of its inhabitants. This cannot ignore the positive and negative local peculiarities. The project not only wants to talk about the successes and best practices but wants to offer data and insights that can help other cities in the future to overcome the obstacles previously encountered and described in the research that will arise from IN-HABIT.

'**Realism**' is the keyword of a **local-to-global communication**. A communication approach that is able to describe in a realistic way how the ability to grasp and overcome local challenges can profoundly impact the local dimension and give impetus to other cities, at the same time representing correctly and truthfully how to overcome some of the obstacles that, in what is proposed by the decision makers, can block the decision to implement a transformation in many places in the world, is a key starting point to open the dialogue with those who every day are confronted with barriers and limits to the transformation of cities. IN-HABIT's local-to-global communication must tell decision makers, cities around the world and their inhabitants, local actors, that more liveable and inclusive cities are a perspective, not without criticality, but realistic and that the change is a viable choice if it occurs through collaboration and that the effort employed is worthwhile.

In the IN-HABIT project, the partners in a broader sense, our local stakeholders, the communities, the neighbourhood, the cities and above all their inhabitants are protagonists to the story.

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With the support of **local communicators and local observers**, successes and debates in cities can become discussion topics for a wider audience through:

- the website page dedicated to each city;
- strategies created ad hoc to emphasise the local projects connected to IN-HABIT;
- coordinated press office activities;
- IN-HABIT newsletters;
- the outreach and dissemination actions defined within the project;
- the presence at events and conferences as representatives of the IN-HABIT project.

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3. Guidelines for an accessible and unique DECO Strategy

3.1 Modular framework and approach (topic by groups)

Within IN-HABIT, each stakeholder – general or local – can become a target, each target can become a storyholder, each partner can become a spokesperson and each beneficiary can become a stakeholder or an institutional partner. For this reason, those who communicate must always ask themselves:

- What effect do I want to generate through my communication?
- What response and level of involvement do I expect from the recipients of my communication?
- How can I better understand the expectations of others to get my message across?
- What tools and motivations can I give to my recipients so that they choose to become active in the project?
- How can the recipients in turn carry the message to subsequent recipients?

Communication is always modular, target-based, defined on the main objective and the real knowledge of the recipients' expectations and motivation at that particular moment.

At the local level, communication must touch global topics as well as local issues of direct interest and must activate the thought that local issues can become of global interest and that global ones are always of local interest.

At the centre of all IN-HABIT communications from project stakeholders and third entities, it is essential to always recall:

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- the general project description and the global vision;
- the four key values;
- the local objective in relation to the global objective or the research objective in relation to the global objective and its location in specific areas;
- what the target of the moment can do to take action, according to possibilities and level of involvement.

This is also valid for organisations that participate in IN-HABIT without having a link with a specific territory in which the research takes place (for example, universities, SMEs, research centres).

3.2 Inclusivity: guidelines

Inclusiveness is one of the guiding values of IN-HABIT both in internal and external communication.

- Preventing sexism, racism, social and gender biases through a neutral but inclusive communication.
- Gender equality must be represented in each communication about the IN-HABIT choices regarding the project.
- Taking into account the characteristics and the social/cultural features of different cultures.
- Taking into account the capacity of accessing the communication of different social groups (about this, the IN-HABIT project aims to put global and EU debate in people's day-to-day lives, the language used for the communication will be accessible to non-experts and will avoid any reference to the EU jargon and technical terms).
- Communication through video should be translated (subtitles).
- Local channels should have a central role in reaching out to groups of categories and collectives at risk of exclusion.

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Regarding the risk of possible bias in online conversation, with the support of experts involved in the project (UREAD, WP6 leaders and other PPs) a **common framework** will be created, and appropriate answers to posts and comments will be provided, through the G&D Toolkit.

3.3 Unique Communication mandate: wording and meanings

It is essential that IN-HABIT's communication is **consistent**. In order for a large number of partners and stakeholders to communicate both with each other and externally, giving the same meaning to the words, a glossary has been defined in collaboration with the partner Tesserae, to later be included in this document as an Annex.

The actions that make the communication mandate unique also depend on:

- the ability to correctly and completely inform people who approach the project for the first time from the first contact (also referring to all IN-HABIT communication channels);
- the ability to convey a certain mindset through practical actions: the way in which choices are made communicates the project probably more than words can (so, for example, it is important to be credible in talking about inclusion, the buzz around the project will really make it clear that inclusive onboarding choices are being made, or talking about the effectiveness of actions will be credible if precision in measuring the results in order to improve them etc. is demonstrated);
- the attention not to neglect correct and complete training and information to all those who become part of the project, even if they spend little time or do it voluntarily and not constantly: do not allow the personal interpretation of a collaborator to become the frame of the story;
- attention to not allowing incorrect interpretations, it is better to always clarify with kindness and simplicity what could cause misunderstanding.

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In this regard, a **position paper** of simple questions and answers concerning the project, its purposes, who it is addressed to, and all the information that may be relevant can be prepared and disseminated among the partners starting from the most frequent questions and misunderstanding and engaging in a co-design process with them.

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4. Stakeholder Engagement Actions

Every communication tool and every communication opportunity must be organised to host an explicit "call to action" that **invites groups to participate** in the project taking into account different possible levels of involvement.

In general, the target can:

- stay up to date on the project (by subscribing to the general newsletter, following social profiles);
- participate in social media communication through comments;
- share the project with friends and acquaintances (via email and inviting them to like them on social networks);
- submit thoughts on the project or how it could be more effective – constructive feedback is always welcome;
- request direct contact to join the project on a local basis and become a volunteer;
- request direct contact for the project element as a partner and make tools and spaces available;
- introduce an interested stakeholder or partner;
- propose a collaboration with a specific project that involves as a citizen or as a contact person for an organisation;
- propose a collaboration with a specific project that also involves other stakeholders;
- apply the search results locally.

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Likewise, in all multi-channel communication actions, the proactivity of the targets must be encouraged through, for example:

- Communication aimed at highlighting the activities of stakeholders that aim to raise awareness on value topics relevant to IN-HABIT
- Communication regarding the results of research conducted by third entities considered relevant for the project
- Specific communications that give visibility to those who offer their support as a partner and to the initiative created within the collaboration (also through the launch of joint press releases)
- The visibility of the activities carried out by those who are volunteers in the project
- The presentation of the people who collaborate in the project
- Incentives to share on social networks and newsletters (for example, incentivising turn-based PPs to share social pages or special content with their followers)

The communication formats are very important to ensure continuity in the relationship with the public who are not involved (or not yet ready to get involved in the project).

For this reason, it is advisable that the contents aimed at this specific target are those that do not require a high level of attention to be enjoyed and that the stories that are told are divided into "**episodes**", precisely in order to create a **recurring relationship**.

Finally, local communication managers and facilitators should always be proactive towards new targets and clear on the opportunities to take part in the project, draw up declarations of interest and organise feedback closely, as well as being informed about all new opportunities of participation that open with the passing of the months. A **degree of flexibility** must be allowed concerning local communication and dissemination activities. Interaction among WP8 leaders and partners will ensure constant **cross-checking** of differences that might affect coherence.

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4.1 Attract the media attention

To ensure that the information distributed to the press, radio and TV is interesting, the news will be subjected to a **double-check** together with the local communications manager.

To make sure news is attractive to the press, communicators in charge will double-check that:

- the organisation that disseminates the news is also a primary or institutional source of the news, ascertainable and accredited;
- the news is true and unpublished, recent;
- the news concerns people in relevant positions;
- the news has an impact on a vast territorial area and on a conspicuous number of individuals;
- the fact has relevance in the present day or as a function of future developments;
- the news has relevance for the target of the newspaper that is asked to disseminate it;
- the content is of quality: the numbers are fundamental;
- the format in which the news is spread is appealing to the audience of the media chosen;
- the Tone of Voice of the news is suitable for the media audience to which it is addressed for dissemination.

4.2 IN-HABIT events and participation in conferences organised by third entities

The events planned so far that will be organised by IN-HABIT at a general, comprehensive level are:

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- The presentation events of the project in each city, at the moment of the establishment of the IN-HUBS
- The final event

Of course, cities are encouraged to organise and foster **local events** in their own neighbourhood to promote the project aims. Although it is expected that IN-HABIT representatives will be involved in EU events, conferences and local workshops on the main topics and labs.

The conferences in which the representatives of IN-HABIT are expected to be involved are those that concern the main topics of the project and are organised by third parties. Recurrences and external events promoted by European institutions, partners and clustering and sister projects have already been mapped (and are available on the document sharing platform for internal communication). This helps with staying up-to-date and with the development of communication strategies that make IN-HABIT **actively involved** in the most important public debates on reference topics and relevant for stakeholders sensitive to them.

It is recommended that everyone involved reports to the WP8 leaders any **opportunity for participation** or invitation to present the project in these initiatives that enjoy great visibility far enough in advance to allow their evaluation, the possible integration of participation in the event in the communication strategy and completion of all related arrangements both from the bureaucratic point of view and from the planning of stakeholder relations actions and joint communication with other partners before, during and after the conference.

In this regard, an open calendar will be made available, and an open repository to encourage reporting of local, national and international events has been created and shared with PPs.

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4.2.1 Local Workshops and events

In the same way, it is highly recommended to partners that they encourage the participation of IN-HABIT representatives in workshops and local initiatives that are promoted by cities, provinces, regions, scientific bodies, universities and which can **increase the awareness** of the project and offer **opportunities for involvement** of further stakeholders and local partners who can become **active ambassadors** in multiplying the project's messages. This calendar will be updated throughout the project lifetime.

In the event of participation in external events or congresses, partners will communicate a few days in advance all the relevant details (title, date, place and link) to WP8 leaders to allow pre-, post- and of course real-time coverage through all the media (website, social networks in pre- and follow ups and twitter in real-time wherever possible and relevant).

Labs dedicated to each target would be organised if feasible, in particular:

- Labs to enable
- Labs to involve
- Labs to engage
- Labs to disseminate

At the moment, given the current uncertain situation, a detailed plan for these labs, which will be conducted along with the relevant PPs (LCREA, for instance), is not yet available. Generally speaking, labs to enable will be conducted taking advantage of online tools on a prevalent digital approach in 2021 at least, focusing on basic “how to” tools in communications and FAQ sessions to be held with local communicators and observers.

Other labs would be youth grassroot communication ones, planned for the beginning of 2022, aimed at involving young adults in the process of communicating the project in their local contexts and disseminating local initiatives.

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Other labs to engage and enable storytelling might be organised with children and schools later on during the project lifetime.

Labs are useful because they allow the targets, based on their interests and skills, to **learn new notions**, stay informed, **develop new skills** and experience practical ways to keep the project objectives alive during and after it. The workshops will be defined in accordance with the PPs in order to maintain an effective approach aimed at **maximising involvement** in the project.

Regarding the specific goal of crafting a plan of events to support the scientific dissemination, a first overview of **potential scientific dissemination channels** and of other urban events in which results will be presented can be found below:

Conferences and upcoming events (to be updated):

- EU GREEN WEEK – Lathi May 2021
- European Free Leaf Award to be assigned (open to towns with 20,000 to 100, 000 inhabitants with good practices of green sustainability). The 2021 European Green Leaf title was jointly awarded to Gabrovo in Bulgaria and Lappeenranta in Finland. For 2020, the European Green Leaf title was jointly awarded to Limerick in Ireland and Mechelen in Belgium.
- IWA World Water Congress – Water for smart liveable cities, May 2021
- Estonia: Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP) Europe Conference, June 2021
- Poland: Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit, June 2021
- University of Oxford: NBS Conference, July 2021
- Poland: 3rd World Conference of the Society for Urban Ecology, July 2021
- France: IUCN World Conservation Congress, September 2021
- UN Climate Change Conference, November 2021
- Oxford: NBS Solutions in a Changing Climate, July 2022

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European Capital of Culture and related events in the following cities

- 2020 (title might be extended to 2021 due to COVID-19 to give opportunity to visit) Rijeka, Galway, Parma
- 2021 Timișoara, Elefsina, Novi Sad
- 2022 Kaunas, Esch-sur-Alzette

Green Capitals

- 2021 Lathi
- 2022 Grenoble

Youth European capitals

- 2021 Kaipėda
- 2022 Tirana

Sports European capitals

- 2021 Lisbon
- 2022 The Hague

Other events

- ROCK project – RISE IMET INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE 2021 (Emerging Technologies and the Digital Transformation of Museums and Heritage Sites), Cyprus, June 2021
- Connecting Nature Summit Series – Innovation Summit, Glasgow, March 2021

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- Urban Arena Berlin: Governance for Sustainable and Just Cities, Berlin, March 2021
- REWAISE: 29th Topical Meeting on Energy and Water, April 2021
- Global Water Summit 2021, May 2021

International Days

- 21/03/21 International day for the elimination of racial discrimination 2021 and International day of forests
- 22/03/21 World Water Day
- 24/03/21 International Day for the Right to the Truth Concerning Gross Human Rights Violations and for the Dignity of Victims
- 02/04/21 World Autism Awareness Day
- 07/04/21 World Health Day
- 21/04/21 International Creativity and Innovation Day in 2021
- 22/04/21 Earth Day 2021
- 01/05/21 International Workers' Day
- 22/05/21 International Day for Biological Diversity
- 05/06/21 World Environmental Day
- 20/06/21 World Refugees Day
- 22/06/21 World Rainforest Day
- 26/06/21 UN International Day in Support of Victims of Torture
- 03/07/21 The International Plastic Bag Free Day
- 23/09/21 International Day of Sign Languages
- 04/10/21 World Habitat Day – World Animal Day
- 17/10/21 International Day for the Eradication of poverty
- 31/10/21 World Cities Day
- 03/12/21 International Day of Persons with Disabilities
- 10/12/21 Human Rights Day
- 20/12/21 International Human Solidarity Day

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International Reference journals in Urban studies: International Journal of Urban and Regional Research, Journal of Urban Economics, Urban Studies, City, Urban Sciences, Sustainable Cities, Cities, European Urban and Regional Studies, International Journal of the Commons, Ecology and Society, Journal of Innovative Research in Sciences, Engineering and Technology.

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5. Validation, monitoring, tracking, reporting and evaluation in communication.

In the day-to-day, the impact and performance of the project's communication actions need to be monitored, tracked, measured and reported.

But what are the **most relevant metrics** to keep an eye on?

5.1 Online

Possibly through a **digital tool** which can monitor and track data (i.e., Meltwater application for press and Hootsuite for social media), help in creating reports and in giving a first evaluation of the performance (social media and online media), in particular around campaigning times and in general considering updates every 6 or 12 months. Digital tools can automate the process to **save time** and get a **clear and correct overview**.

Social Media, possible KPIs. e.g., Quantitative Number of clicks, likes, shares, tags, video views, new followers, profile visits, engagement rates, cost per result, use of hashtags and influence of the accounts that use it etc. e.g., Qualitative Types of comments received, their tone, the number of people they reached, the types of followers, impressions, traffic data, ratings, word clouds, sentiment analysis.

Website. Visitors and unique users, origin of the traffic, number and type of visitors, referent sites.

Newsletter. Performance (newsletter opens, clicks, shares, etc.)

PR traction, possible KPIs. Mentions, quality of the articles, tone (positive, negative, neutral), reach, reliability of information, importance of the media, adequacy of the target audience,

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position of the article, possible sharing of the content on social network accounts, reactions to the article, agenda building skills.

5.2 Offline

IN-HABIT institutional role: presence in relevant institutional events, effectiveness of institutional meetings and institutional communications opportunities, good mentions, awards.

Stakeholder relations: local network opportunities and values that generate, new stakeholders/month, new active collaborations.

Participation: new volunteers, new projects born, new ongoing proposal-activities, number of causes actively supported.

Local: KPI based on specific achievement in social inclusion (e.g., new tools and services provided to disadvantaged groups), number of moments of education shared, number of IN-HABIT activities replicated by local organisations, new local channels.

In particular, a set of KPIs has been defined to monitor the **successful deployment** in terms of **efficiency and effectiveness** of communication and dissemination activities.

These indicators comprise:

Table 4: IN-HABIT KPIs.

Outputs/KPIs	Measurement Unit	Target Value
Project Website	-	1
App published	-	1
Project Visual Identity	-	1

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Project DECO strategy	-	1
City communication pack	Number of items	4
Policy guidelines for the replication of VIS that enhance IHW	-	1
Replicable Business Model to boost IHW	-	1
Project brochure	Number of items	5
Newsletters launched	Number of launches	50
Press launch	Number of launches	10
Launch about IN-HUBs established in each city	Number of launches	4
Co-designed workshop designed in each city	Number of workshops	8
Business exploitation meetings	Number of business exploitation meetings	10
Presentation Video	Number of videos	1
Video for local use	Number of clips	5
Number of events attended as a guest	Number of events	10
Number of events organised directly by the project (campaigns)	Number of events	5
Scientific publications	Number of mentions	10
Resources shared (informative material)	Number of resources	25
External audiences of the website*	Unique visitors	30,000

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Posts of dissemination on Facebook*	Facebook Posts	500
Posts of dissemination on LinkedIn*	Facebook	500
Tweets*	Number of tweets	100
Number on Facebook followers provided by the partners*	Followers	3000
Press release articles published by media and detected in the press review	Clip Articles of press review	200
Dissemination activities by partners	Activities/partner	5
Local events provided by partners	Number of local events/partner	10
Activities of dissemination in IN-HABIT website on the pages of the cities*	Number of blog posts	20
Number of events attended representing the project	Number of the events	10
New volunteers/city	Number of volunteers/city	10
Number of local causes actively supported	Number of causes	5

Table 4: IN-HABIT KPIs.

*to be updated

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Scientific Dissemination: KPI

Table 5: IN-HABIT Scientific Dissemination KPIs.

Outputs/KPI s	Measurement Unit	Target Value
Number of IN-HABIT solutions replicated/cities interested in replicating	Number of mentions in press release	3
Number of events where results are presented	Number of events	10
Number of dissemination actions developed by the cities	Action/city	10
Number of dissemination actions developed by the network involved (key local contacts and support personnel)	Number of actions	5
Number of newsletters on the research results	Number of newsletters	10
Press launch dedicated to research and solutions with decision-makers	Number of launches	10
Number of infographics on the research results on the social	Number of posts	20

Table 5: IN-HABIT Scientific Dissemination KPIs.

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6. Internal communication

Structured internal communication is essential so that all strategic fine-tuning opportunities are exploited, communication, exploitation dissemination and outreach activities take place in a **coordinated manner** according to a **timeline** that is clear to all partners and to improve the communicative performance of the project making it attractive for every target and on every presentation occasion.

To make this possible, all PPs have been given access to a folder, which will be updated by WP8 leaders in particular, that includes:

- The DECO strategy
- The visual identity and guidelines and materials (project templates, logos, iconography, fonts, references imagery)
- Communication guidelines
- The internal contacts, which is recommended to be kept updated with the names and emails of the contact people for operational activities (communication, translations for the cities), with the contacts for the various research areas and any other relevant contacts and updated addresses of websites and social media profiles
- The multi-channel communication plan and in particular the social publishing plan
- A stakeholder map to be drawn up jointly with partners
- The calendar of events, in which it is recommended any manifestation of interest in advance is reported
- The logos of the organisations
- The press kit and authorised photos
- The press review and corresponding repository
- The collection of brochures and all executive of official communication materials
- The list of EU reference sources for Horizon 2020 projects on communication

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- A folder to share ideas, articulate winds of interest to keep an eye on

It is also recommended that the PPs **promptly update** and **integrate** these shared materials whenever data and information change or can be updated to allow the information shared and used by other partners to always be **correct and consistent**.

Finally, the PPs are expected to be the first to be involved. PPs should remember:

- to follow IN-HABIT profiles and hashtags;
- to communicate to the WP8 leaders their social profiles and websites;
- to communicate to the WP8 leaders any relevant profiles and websites to follow and to keep in touch with;
- to invite followers to follow the IN-HABIT profiles (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, YouTube and eventual other social channels used at a local level);
- to share each IN-HABIT post with their communities;
- to share relevant information and events WP8 leaders could include in the communication strategy.

Table 6: IN-HABIT project partners and contact information for communication.

Partner	Communication contacts	Website	Twitter	Facebook	Instagram	LinkedIn
1. UNIVERSIDAD DE CÓRDOBA, UCO, Spain	isotta.macfadden@uco.es	http://www.uco.es/	https://twitter.com/Univcordoba	https://www.facebook.com/universidadcordoba	https://www.instagram.com/universidaddecordoba/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/universidad-de-cordoba/
2. AYUNTAMIENTO DE CÓRDOBA, CORD, Spain	Blanca.torrent@ayuncordoba.es	https://www.cordoba.es/	https://twitter.com/ayuncordoba_es	https://www.facebook.com/ayuncordoba.es		

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3. ASOCIACIÓN VECINAL UNION Y ESPERANZA DE LAS PALMERAS, AVUE, Spain	unionyesperanza@yahoo.com					
4. NODIBINAJUMS BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE, BSC, Latvia	Sandra.sumane@gmail.com	http://www.bscresearch.lv	https://twitter.com/BalticCentre			
5. RIGAS PLANOSANAS REGIONS, RPR, Latvia	aija.zucika@rpr.gov.lv , katrina.valaine@rpr.gov.lv	http://rpr.gov.lv/ http://rpr.gov.lv/project/in-habit/ : updates and results about the project IN-HABIT		https://www.facebook.com/rigasplanosanasregions		
6. BC MANUFABKTURA, KQ, Latvia						
7. UNIVERSITA DI PISA, UNIPI, Italy	inhabit@vet.unipi.it c.borrelli2@studenti.unipi.it	www.unipi.it				
8. COMUNE DI LUCCA, LUCCA, Italy	nadia.davini@gmail.com	www.comune.lucca.it				
9. LUCCA CREA SRL, LCREA, Italy		www.luccacreat.it				
10. SLOVENSKA POLNOHOSPODARSKA UNIVERZITA V NITRE, SUA, Slovakia	michal.hrivnak@hotmail.com	https://www.uninag.sk/en/main-page/				

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11. MESTO NITRA, NITRA, Slovakia		https://www.nitra.sk/				
12. TRIPTYCH, HIDE, Slovakia						
13. THE UNIVERSITY OF READING, UREAD, United Kingdom	m.dellagiusta@rdg.ac.uk	http://www.reading.ac.uk/				
14. ISIMPACT, ISIM, Italy	paola.dilazzaro@isimpact.it	https://www.isimpact.org/				
15. TESSERAE, TSR, Germany	luismi@tesserae.eu	http://www.tesserae.eu	@tesseraeUSR			
16. BRIDGE FOR BILLIONS SL, B4B, Spain	pablo@bridgeforbillions.org	https://bridgeforbillions.org/				
17. DESIGN FOR CHANGE ESPANA, DFC Spain	beatriz@dfcspain.org	https://www.dfcspain.org/	@dfcspain	@dfcspain	@dfcspain	Design for Change España
18. BOOK ON A TREE LTD, BOT, United Kingdom	projects@bookonatre.com , inhabitweb@bookonatre.com , inhabitsocial@bookonatre.com , press@bookonatre.com	www.bookonatre.com				
19. BELGISCH LABORATORIUM VAN DE ELEKTRICITEITSINDUSTRIE LABORELEC CVBA,	rob.vanheur@engie.com , agathe.pharel@engie.com	https://www.laborelec.com/				Personal Profiles of the referents: Agathe: https://www.linkedin.com/in/agathe-pharel-01041a10b/

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LABORELEC, Belgium						Rob: https://www.linkedin.com/in/robyan-heur-3082216/
20. WELLNESS TELECOM SL, WTG, Spain		https://wellnessg.com/en/				
21. PONTIFICIA UNIVERSIDAD JAVERIANA, PUJ, Colombia		https://www.javeriana.edu.co/inicio	personal profile Yunda: @juanyunda Olga: @Olgaceballos 19			

Table 6: IN-HABIT project partners and contact information for communication

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7. Quality assessment and Risk analysis

The risk analysis plan is implemented and monitored by the communications team at BOT, in close relation to the lead coordinator UCO and to partner WTG that is co-responsible as the partner of dissemination actions, to ensure that **proper and immediate mitigation measures** are foreseen to solve and mitigate any possible issues.

Table 7: Quality assessment and risk analysis.

KPI-Actions to reach the target	Risks	Mitigation actions
<p>Active strategy of networking, dissemination of activities and results, involvement of local and visitors, awareness raising and promotion of IN-HABIT</p> <p>Partners fully committed to disseminating IN-HABIT practices in all the forums and networks where they participate</p> <p>Several city networks at international and national levels have been contacted and have shown their interest in IN-HABIT results through support letters. BOT will follow up these actions contacting press departments of different networks to attract their attention/collaborate with IN-HABIT once the project is in capacity</p>	<p>Poor performance of IN-HABIT proposed visionary and integrated solutions to address IHW needs in cities</p> <p>Lack of interest of city networks in IN-HABIT results</p>	<p>Interactive website</p> <p>Attractive set of dissemination layouts</p> <p>IN-HABIT goals and outcomes align with major actual urban challenges</p> <p>Healthy urban development and IHW as a priority for most cities</p> <p>INHABIT-APP easily adapted to the needs of other cities and establishing a two-way communication between citizens and PP</p>
<p>Local events to make communities aware provided in digital environment because of the pandemic measures</p>	<p>Digital-divide, lack of access to digital for categories at risk of exclusion</p>	<p>Settle into the channels used locally by the local services and Municipality to spread useful information or entertainment</p> <p>Each event should also contain training and tools to enable targets to use digital more frequently and also after the end of the project, opportunity</p>

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		to switch to the offline mode for events if the local regulation allows it
Increase the legitimacy of the project in the consideration of local communities	Citizens will not recognise the solutions as a European intervention but as only a local policy	Use of EU disclaimer in the communication asset, spread correct information about how the project is related to European Institutions intervention and how it impacts at a local level
Involve the City Halls and their policymakers in the IN-HABIT project	Changes in the composition of the City Halls and lack of interest in the project	IN-HABIT focus on important challenges in all the cities. Different policymakers have shown their interest in the project. Visionary and integrated solutions will improve health and wellbeing in the cities
Involve local stakeholders in the establishment of the IN-HUBs	Lack of participation of local stakeholders in the IN-HUBs	Different stakeholders have already been contacted and have shown their interest in participating in all the cities
Involve in co-design workshops	Limited interest in the co-design workshops	Colini-Tripodi partner has extensive experience in citizen engagement in deprived areas. City partners will have a proactive role to boost participation
Activate co-design workshops	Less than satisfactory results in the co-design workshops	Colini-Tripodi and city partners will work with experts (architects, designers, engineers) and produce appealing simulations to facilitate the work
Deploy hard Visionary and Integrated Solutions	Delays in the deployment of hard Visionary and Integrated Solutions	The cities will start the procedures at the beginning of the project and will work with reliable contractors
Deploy hard Visionary and Integrated Solutions	Higher costs than expected in the deployment of hard Visionary and Integrated Solutions	The budget has been adjusted to actual prices. Ways to solve unexpected rise of costs will be explored, from municipal budgets to crowdsourcing or private financial support
Boost the participation in the deployment of soft visionary and integrated solutions	Lack of participation in the deployment of soft visionary and integrated solutions	TSR partner has an extensive experience in citizen engagement in deprived areas. City partners will have a proactive role to boost participation
Deploy platform	Delays in the deployment of the platform	WTG has a long experience in the running of platforms

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Share the IN-HABIT project and involve inhabitants	Lack of interests of other city inhabitants in IN-HABIT project	IN-HABIT to tackle issues of great concerns and interest actually. Visionary and integrated solutions deployed in emblematic places. Activities designed to draw attraction
Involve people in behavioural games	Limited interest and impact of the behavioural games	UREAD has a proven experience in the use of behavioural games. Together with TSR will design an attractive strategy to engage people
Make people actively participate to measure health and wellbeing	Reluctance to participate in the activities to measure health and wellbeing	ISIM and ATBI together with the community activators will design different incentives to motivate people to participate. Participation will deliver health and wellbeing benefits to citizens
Spread IN-HABIT method and planning	Unwillingness of city planners and civil servants to accept IN-HABIT methods and planning frameworks	City Halls fully involved in the project. Other authorities have shown their support. Methods and framework will prove their usefulness and interest for urban authorities and planners
Spread IN-HABIT vision	Lack of interest in replicating 13 IN-HABIT visionary and integrated solutions	IN-HABIT visionary and integrated solutions will attract attention. We will deliver good practices, lessons learnt and paths to overcome barriers. Intensive communication and dissemination campaigns will be launched
Communicate in a clear way who the PPs are and how they give value	Changes in the project Consortium	Surveillance to detect it as soon as possible. Request from the partners network a substitute with equivalent (or higher) qualifications. Exploit a common strategy to communicate it
Making the local community perceive that IN-HABIT is an EU funded project	Unclear funding communication	Follow up to detect and minimise risk as soon as possible in all local initiatives.

Table 7: Quality assessment and risk analysis.

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8. Timeline and work plan

In order to achieve the objectives set out by the Agreement according to the guidelines of this DC plan and DECO Strategy, a **timeline of actions** concerning the first eighteen months of the project is presented below.

The actions, as anticipated, have been defined at a stage in which the pandemic emergency is still ongoing and it is difficult to predict its evolution, so for this reason **online channels** have been privileged. This does not exclude that, in the event of the emergency being resolved, the same actions may be implemented offline, also in order to guarantee **access** and the involvement and **inclusion** of all those targets affected by the digital divide or who do not have access and familiarity with digital channels.

In this regard, it is recommended to the PPs that it is always kept up to date on the opportunities for **expanding initiatives in the offline environment** that were initially designed only for online and vice versa, always referring to the communication leader.

The actions have been defined also taking into consideration that the cities need more time to set the local establishment of the IN-HUBS and, at the same time, the need to communicate the project in 2021 through a first public campaign.

The DC plan and DECO Strategy is a **living document**, to be updated regularly.

Its main actions and its timeline may be found below:

January/February 2021: leaflet – short version

February/March 2021: training for local community activators (led by WP5)

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End of February 2021: DECO plan final delivery

March 2021:

- Website – first release
- Start to plan the project kit

April 2021:

- DECO local specification – with the project Glossary, the G&D Toolkit
- Start to plan the second release of the website

June 2021:

- First communication general campaign on the IN-HABIT project. A press kit will be shared among the cities and a launch on online reviews will be done. Start of coordinated public relations local activities.
- One short promotional video about the project, to be combined with four short local teaser videos (to be used in launch campaign for local customised dissemination)
- Website – second release

September 2021:

- Leaflet – local versions
- Start to plan the third release of the website

From October 2021 to the end of February 2022: IN-HABIT launched in each city and public relations activities (communication pack) and following events of presentation.

December 2021:

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- Website – third release
- Finalise a more complete communication pack
- Instagram and YouTube channels to be implemented

From January 2022: INHABIT-APP – Discussion on initial requirements scheduled for Jan 2021, preliminary development 2021-early 2022.

June 2022: testing INHABIT-APP

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Annexes

Annex 1. IN-HABIT Visual identity, project templates and graphic package

Annex 2. IN-HABIT Communication Guidelines

Annex 3. European Commission references on Communication & Dissemination

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LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: IN-HABIT's project participants.

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Figure 2: The IN-HABIT partnership.

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Figure 3: Comprehensive Stakeholder Mapping.

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Figure 4: timeline of website releases (2-3).

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IN-HABIT

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OUR LOGO

The multi-coloured logo is the primary brand mark for IN-HABIT. In the following pages, you'll learn how the logo can be used to ensure consistency across all touchpoints.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

The dark blue logo is the correct logo for formal situations of the IN-HABIT identity.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

In addition to the primary and secondary logos, the following colourways can also be used for the logo.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

LIGHT BLUE

RED

YELLOW

GREEN

BLACK

WHITE

The protected area keeps the IN-HABIT logo free from other text or graphic elements that could compromise its legibility or recognition. The height of the H from the IN-HABIT logo should be used to define the protected area around the margins.

Coloured versions of the IN-HABIT logo should **not** be used over a coloured background or image. In these situations, use the white version.

COLOUR BACKGROUND

The white version of the IN-HABIT logo must be used over a coloured background.

IMAGE BACKGROUND

The white version of the IN-HABIT logo must be used over images.

Example of incorrect use of the primary logo over an image

Below are some IN-HABIT logo application examples that follow the rules set out on the previous page.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

Example of the primary IN-HABIT logo being used in a PowerPoint document

WORD DOCUMENT

Example of the primary IN-HABIT logo being used in the header of a Word document

SOCIAL MEDIA ASSET

Example of the white IN-HABIT logo being used over an image for use on social media

Below are some violations of the brand guidelines.
Note: these examples don't cover all possible violations.

Do **not** stretch or distort the logo

Do **not** apply a different colour to the logo to those described in this chapter

Do **not** change the position of any of the logo's elements

Do **not** overlay graphic elements or text over the logo

Do **not** use a gradient background that compromises the logo's legibility

Do **not** apply a gradient to the logo

Do **not** apply a drop shadow to the logo

Do **not** recreate the primary logo in grayscale

IN-HABIT is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union and, where appropriate, this should be communicated on brand material via the EU flag and associated copy below. There are two versions:

[Download the EU flag graphics: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

[Read the EU communication toolkit: https://bit.ly/2NGdeER](https://bit.ly/2NGdeER)

CO-FUNDED (WHITE BACKGROUND)

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

GRANT (WHITE BACKGROUND)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

CO-FUNDED (COLOURED BACKGROUND OR IMAGE)

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

GRANT (COLOURED BACKGROUND OR IMAGE)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

The EU flag and accompanying text can be used over photography where there is enough reasonable contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should be used over a brand colour when overlaying over photography where there is **not** enough contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should **not** be used over photography where there is not enough contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should be displayed in all IN-HABIT brand documents such as PowerPoint presentations and Word documents.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

The EU flag features at the bottom of each PowerPoint slide

WORD DOCUMENT

The EU flag features in the footer on every page of a Word document

OUR COLOURS

The IN-HABIT primary colours should be the dominant colours used throughout IN-HABIT material. IN-HABIT Formal Blue should be used in formal situations and applications of the IN-HABIT identity.

The CMYK colour values should be used for print applications. The RGB colour values should be used for digital applications. The HEX colour values should be used for web-based applications. Note, the CMYK colours used in print applications will look different compared to the RGB colours used digitally.

IN-HABIT BLUE

CMYK 78 24 0 8
 RGB 36 173 234
 HEX #24ADEA

IN-HABIT RED

CMYK 0 85 92 0
 RGB 239 68 65
 HEX #EF4441

IN-HABIT YELLOW

CMYK 00 00 00 00
 RGB 249 203 88
 HEX #F9CB58

IN-HABIT GREEN

CMYK 60 0 63 0
 RGB 53 229 149
 HEX #35E595

IN-HABIT FORMAL BLUE

CMYK 70 33 0 57
 RGB 33 73 109
 HEX #21496D

BLACK

CMYK 40 40 40 100
 RGB 0 0 0
 HEX #000000

WHITE

CMYK 0 0 0 0
 RGB 255 255 255
 HEX #FFFFFF

The IN-HABIT secondary colours are used for the IN-HABIT brand icons and can also be used as accent colours across various IN-HABIT material.

The CMYK colour values should be used for print applications. The RGB colour values should be used for digital applications. The HEX colour values should be used for web-based applications. Note, the CMYK colours used in print applications will look different compared to the RGB colours used digitally.

LIGHT BLUE

CMYK 83 42 0 0
 RGB 0 126 198
 HEX #007EC6

LIGHT RED

CMYK 9 100 46 2
 RGB 213 2 83
 HEX #D50253

LIGHT YELLOW

CMYK 0 44 71 0
 RGB 249 164 84
 HEX #F9A454

LIGHT GREEN

CMYK 69 0 69 0
 RGB 6 211 122
 HEX #06D37A

DARK BLUE

CMYK 100 86 39 30
 RGB 2 42 90
 HEX #022A5A

DARK RED

CMYK 0 82 51 0
 RGB 249 75 92
 HEX #F94B5C

DARK YELLOW

CMYK 0 67 94 0
 RGB 255 109 1
 HEX #FF6D01

DARK GREEN

CMYK 91 36 100 34
 RGB 0 91 35
 HEX #005B23

Each city has a primary IN-HABIT brand colour assigned to it based on the dominant colour of the country's flag. This should be the dominant colour use for any city-specific material (for example, backgrounds of text boxes and accent colour).

NITRA (SLOVAKIA)LIGHT BLUE

RIGA (LATVIA)RED

CORDOBA (SPAIN)YELLOW

LUCCA (ITALY)GREEN

OUR TYPOGRAPHY

The primary typeface for all IN-HABIT materials is Nunito. Where it's not possible to use Nunito, Calibri should be used. Note: Nunito and Calibri should **never** be used together in any application.

[Download the Nunito brand fonts: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

PRIMARY TYPEFACE

NUNITO

REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

FALLBACK TYPEFACE

CALIBRI

REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Nunito Bold should always be used for titles and short bits of text that need to stand out. Nunito Regular should always be used for body copy. The same applies to Calibri, if Nunito can't be used.

TITLE TEXT

Titles should be set in **all caps** and **bold** weight.

Body text

Body text should be set in **sentence case** and **regular** weight.

The slide features a blue header with the 'IN-HABIT' logo in the top left corner. The main content area is white with a large, faint, light-blue abstract graphic of interconnected circles and lines on the right side. The text is arranged as follows:

- TITLE GOES HERE** (in all caps, bold weight)
- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Praesent tortor lectus, laoreet a laoreet ac, vulputate id libero. Nunc nulla nunc, blandit nec sem a, consectetur venenatis nisi. Integer sit amet tempus nibh. Suspendisse ac condimentum libero. Nunc hendrerit mi ac aliquam posuere.

At the bottom left, there is a small European Union logo and text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 695227". The number "3" is in the bottom right corner.

Example PowerPoint presentation slide

OUR ICONS

We have a suite of brand icons that can be used to help illustrate and visualise information throughout the various brand applications.

📄 **Download the brand icons:** <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

Note, we have a suite of brand icons available in a PowerPoint template for immediate use.

The brand icons are available to use in the following brand colours.

BLUE

RED

YELLOW

GREEN

BLACK

WHITE

The icon(s) can be any of the brand colours stated on the previous page (except for white) when used on a white background.

The icon(s) should always be white when used over a coloured background and image.

Example of an icon being used in a PowerPoint presentation

Example of icons being used in a PowerPoint presentation

OUR PATTERN

Our brand pattern can be used across various brand applications.

[Download the brand patterns: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

MULTICOLOURED PATTERN

YELLOW

GREEN

RED

LIGHT BLUE

DARK BLUE

Our brand pattern can be used as a background across various brand applications.

PATTERN USE

Example of the multicoloured pattern being used in a PowerPoint presentation

Where text is laid over the top of a pattern, a text box in one of the brand colours must be used with white text.

Don't overlay text over the brand pattern without a coloured text box behind the text

Similarly, the graphic that makes up the pattern can be used on its own as a background across various brand applications.

GRAPHIC USE

Example of the graphic being used in a PowerPoint presentation

The graphic can also be used at 10% opacity of any of the brand colours.

Don't use a text colour that doesn't have reasonable contrast with the pattern or graphic colour behind it

OUR IMAGES

Along with the use of the brand colours and icons, image use is an integral part of the IN-HABIT brand identity. Images can convey a message or a mood within the overall IN-HABIT brand and should focus on people or places.

🔗 Download brand images: <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

Where high-quality stock imagery use isn't possible, "home made" imagery use is allowed where the image is authentic and personable.

Generic stock images that aren't authentic shouldn't be used.

Images can be used standalone or paired with text as a background. If pairing with text, the text must always be clearly legible.

Where images are used for backgrounds with text laid over the top, a text box in one of the brand colours must be used with white text.

Example of an image being used in a PowerPoint presentation

BRAND APPLICATIONS

The IN-HABIT visual identity and graphic package includes:

VISUAL GUIDELINES

A simple tool with examples on how to use logos and imagery, along with dos and don'ts. This how-to guide will help creating consistent projects in line with the IN-HABIT brand.

OUR LOGOS

Our logos in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

OUR ICONS

Our icons in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

OUR PATTERN

Our patterns to be used as background designs for your communication.

NUNITO

OUR TYPOGRAPHY

Our typeface/font.

EU FLAG

The EU flag both in colour and black and white, including the project funding information.

IMAGES

Free images for you to use on your presentations.

The IN-HABIT visual identity and graphic package includes templates in the following formats:

DOCUMENT TEMPLATES

- Press release
- Report
- Meeting agenda
- Meeting minutes
- Deliverable
- Letterhead
- Simple text (free form)

Available in two formats:

- Microsoft Word: downloadable for offline work.
- Google Drive: for documents requiring contribution from many partners. By reducing the number of saved versions, we reduce the potential for errors.

PRESENTATION TEMPLATES

- Formal presentation (for example, for external meetings, conferences, etc.)
- Informal presentation (for internal meetings, etc.)

Available in two formats:

- Lighter version, for download
- Complete version, for online use (like Teams, Drive or other collaborative spaces)
- Icon library (separated - for easier, lighter use)

All templates have been tested and work correctly across several devices. In the folder, you will also find a “how to” guide showing how to add icons, etc. to these templates.

Media-rich presentations are an effective way to connect with your audience. Including high-quality images often adds hugely to audience engagement, but it also increases file size. That means your presentation or file could be too large for some email servers, and it could run a lot slower on some computers.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

To reduce image size in Microsoft PowerPoint:

1. Select a picture, go to the “**Format**” tab and select “**Picture Tools**”.
2. Choose “**Compress Pictures**” in the top left corner. A pop-up box will display your resolution options. For most online purposes, a resolution of 150ppi is fine. If you’re going to print your presentation, choose the print 220ppi option. You can reduce the file size of all images in your presentation by selecting “**Apply to all pictures in the file**”.

Select ‘On-screen (150 ppi)’ picture quality for online purposes

By reducing the resolution of your images your image file sizes are limited, which means your presentation is no larger than it needs to be.

If you’re sending a document by email, convert your presentations into PDF format and use versions with reduced image resolution.

WORD DOCUMENT

To reduce image size in Microsoft Word:

1. Go to the “**File**” tab and select “**Reduce File Size**”.
2. In the pop-up box, select the resolution. For digital, use 150ppi and for printing, use 220ppi. You can reduce the file size of all images in your presentation by selecting “**Apply to all pictures in the file**”.

Select ‘Print (220 ppi)’ picture quality for print purposes

The IN-HABIT primary logo should always be used in Word documents.

 Download Word templates: <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

The IN-HABIT logo should be present in the top-left corner of every slide. The primary logo should always be used when the background is white. The white logo should always be used over a coloured background or image.

Download PowerPoint templates: <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

The white IN-HABIT logo can be used in the top-left corner of photography-based social media assets. The white logo should always be used over a coloured background or image.

When used over white, as in a title bar, the primary logo should be used. When used over an image, use the white logo.

Visit the IN-HABIT website: <https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/>

The roll up designs should follow the visual guidelines with the IN-HABIT logo always placed in the top half and the EU flag and accompanying copy placed at the bottom.

An example of a roll up design using photography

An example of a formal roll up design

Brochure design should follow the visual guidelines. Photography should be used in brochures only if the brochure will be professionally printed; otherwise, a single-coloured pattern should be used.

Below: An example of a brochure design using our brand pattern

Above: An example of a brochure design using photography

COMMUNICATION
GUIDELINES

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020
programme of the European Union

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BRAND POSITIONING

MISSION STATEMENT

We promote inclusive health and wellbeing for people living in four small- and medium-sized cities as innovative solutions for every town across Europe.

INCLUSIVITY

Inclusivity is one of the **core values** of IN-HABIT, and should be a **guiding principle** in both internal and external communication.

SHOW, DON'T TELL

We don't need to mention inclusivity explicitly in our writing to promote it; it should **resonate through the subjects we write about**.

By talking about inclusivity initiatives - whether by IN-HABIT or one of our partners - we communicate how important it is to us.

This means we:

- Take into account the characteristics and the social / cultural features of different cultures.
- Take into account the capacity of accessing the communication of different social groups.
- Translate (subtitles) video communication wherever possible.
- Ensure local channels have a central role in reaching out to groups of categories and collectives at risk of exclusion.

OUR PILLARS

In our communications, we:

Focus on solutions

Stress accessibility

Promote a gender sensitive & inclusive communication

Build bridges in all our communications

Create engaging stories for children and youth

AUDIENCE

WHO WE'RE WRITING FOR:

LOCAL COMMUNITIES

A large part of our audience are people without extensive experience in investment partnerships, like local authorities, entrepreneurs, and associations.

Many of them will be unfamiliar with terms like 'inclusive health and wellbeing', so our writing should educate and explain what they mean.

We should focus on how these initiatives will benefit communities.

Overly formal writing can sound disingenuous. To make our messaging feel authentic, it should be clear, succinct and conversational - like speaking with a friend.

We should tell our audience what they need to know, without including unnecessary or irrelevant details.

WHO WE'RE WRITING FOR:

EU POLICY-MAKERS & COMPREHENSIVE STAKEHOLDERS

Our secondary audience is policy-makers within the European Union, including scientists and researchers, national authorities, policy makers, fellow project partners, and sister projects.

Their understanding and involvement can be essential to our success.

Because they may have varying levels of familiarity with inclusive health and wellbeing and our project's aims, our writing should explain any terms we use clearly.

When writing for this audience, we should focus on the results we have seen or expect to see from IN-HABIT initiatives (for example, community uptake).

PRESS & MEDIA

GUIDELINES

Communication through the press, radio and TV helps us connect with our local communities.

Activities will be led by a central press office coordinated by WP8/BOT that will coordinate the work for four other appointed key contacts and dedicated person supporting BOT during the project lifetime located in the four cities whose contribution will be empowered by the support of local press offices and official channels and spokespeople where available, one month in advance for each launch.

Local contacts are responsible for collecting local press reviews, identifying and reporting on facts relevant to specific projects, and monitoring local events and agendas.

Before contacting the press, make sure you have reviewed and are familiar with the [project kit](#).

GUIDELINES

To make sure news is attractive to the press, communicators in charge will double-check that:

- The organisation that disseminates the news is also a primary or institutional source of the news, ascertainable and accredited.
- The news is true, recent and unpublished.
- The news concerns people in relevant positions.
- The news has an impact on a vast territorial area and on a conspicuous number of individuals.
- The fact has relevance in the present day or as a function of future developments.
- The news has relevance for the target of the newspaper that is asked to disseminate it.
- The content is of quality: the numbers are fundamental.
- The format in which the news is spread is appealing to the audience of the media chosen.
- The tone of voice of the news is suitable for the media audience to which it is addressed for dissemination.

PROJECT KIT

Your project kit contains:

- Summary of each project, values, participants, milestones
- Accurate and updated information on consortium partners
- Profiles of official and local spokespersons
- Database of authorised photos (of people, places, events), of images and of videos and frames free of copyright that can be shared with the press.

SOCIAL MEDIA

USING HASHTAGS

Hashtags are a powerful way for people to find common interests and initiatives on social media.

We can use project-specific hashtags to:

- Increase outreach and join topic-specific conversations
- Capitalise on existing trends (find emerging hashtags to boost the research with the right audiences)
- Group contents to help people find related posts and discussion
- Bring new opinion into a discussion

OUR HASHTAGS

Below you'll find the complete list of IN-HABIT hashtags:

For general use:

- #Cityvolution #HumanSizeCity #INhabiTownns
- #innovatEU #EU4innovation

For local use:

- #EUforCordoba #EUforLucca
- #EUforAgenskalns #EUforNitra
- #CordobaInnovate #LuccaInnovate
- #AgenskalnsInnovate #NitralInnovate

For topics:

- Culture: #CityShareCulture
- Food: #CityGrowsFood
- Nature: #GreenNewCity
- Pets: #CityCareForPets

REFERENCES

Use of common glossary and hashtags through the social profiles: the use of common words is a key practice of IN-HABIT's DECO strategy because it contributes to achieving the goal of creating a shared code with all local and comprehensive stakeholders and beneficiaries of the project since its inception.

A project Glossary and Gender & Diversity Toolkit, also useful for the project in a more holistic sense, will identify keywords that can become relevant for communication on social profiles and that are also significant on the basis of the most recent trending topics on the social networks used, which in the initial phase will be Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter.

TONE OF VOICE

BRAND PERSONALITY

If IN-HABIT was a person, we would be:

Balanced

Curious

Honest

Insider

Open-minded

Engaging

Inclusive

Professional

Explorer

Determined

Aware

BRAND PERSONALITY

The tone of voice in common institutional communications

- ✓ It should be: mid-formal, respectful, empathetic, aware, thoughtful, passionate, enthusiastic, colloquial, advocate (where needed), scientific (in dissemination)
- ✗ It should never be: too self-celebratory (admitted to celebrate the good results of IN-HABIT and the sister and clustering projects), ideological

The tone of voice in local communication

- ✓ It should be: enthusiastic, cheerful, colloquial, engaging, direct, reflective, questioning, reassuring, scientific (in dissemination)
- ✗ It should never be: disinterested, aggressive, indifferent, detached, dominant, ideological

The tone of voice in comprehensive stakeholder and media relations

- ✓ It should be: attentive, informative, direct, reassuring, open, expert, scientific (only for dissemination)
- ✗ It should never be: too solemn, too informal, insecure, ambiguous, wavering, too direct, a “bigmouth”

BRAND PERSONALITY

The tone of voice in communication with young people and children

- ✓ It should be: colloquial, interested, close, open to listening, reassuring, enthusiastic, energetic
- ✗ It should never be: ideological, confused, abrupt, obnoxious, disappointed, sceptical, offended, impatient, condescending, blunt or rough

The tone of voice in communication with collectives at risk of exclusion / disadvantage

- ✓ It should be: neutral, colloquial, thoughtful, direct, reassuring, open minded, encouraging
- ✗ It should never be: abrupt, aggressive, indifferent, aloof, condescending, dominant, cynical, derogatory, desperate, hostile, impatient, aggressive, bored, sarcastic, melancholic, sceptical, impertinent

WRITING GUIDELINES

- Have a specific audience in mind. Who are they? Why do they care about what we're telling them?
- Although your language should adapt to the audience, the IN-HABIT brand personality should remain the same.
- Our goal is to be understood, so try to adapt language to the level of the audience.
- Try to avoid using industry language in public-facing messages. When you need to use technical language, include a simple explanation.
- Use contractions ('we're', not 'we are') to make language more natural and conversational.
- Use active voice, not passive voice ('we will <ACTION>' not '<ACTION> will be done').

WRITING GUIDELINES

- Use British English (organise instead of organize, favourite instead of favorite).
- Locally, use bilingual communication when needed.
- When speaking as IN-HABIT, use 'we' - we talk about ourselves in the first person.
- If you need to use an acronym, make sure you include its definition first. For example, 'IN-HABIT is an EU Horizon 2020 project that aims to foster Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW)...'
- Politically and socially neutral.
- Clear, simple and concise - try to keep sentences under 25 words.
- Once you have finished, read the sentence aloud. Does it sound natural, like speaking to a friend?
- Include a call-to-action! What do you want the audience to do?

REFERENCES

In each of the four pilot cities, the project will mobilise existing undervalued resources to increase health and wellbeing, with a focus on gender, diversity, equity and inclusion (GDE&I). The integrated approach will combine technological, digital, nature-based, cultural, and social innovations in selected urban public spaces.

Please remember this approach should always be included when communicating IN-HABIT aims, experiences and stories.

Please find here some useful references:

EIGE - Toolkit on gender-sensitive communication:
<https://eige.europa.eu/publications/toolkit-gender-sensitive-communication>

GENDER-NEUTRAL LANGUAGE in the European Parliament:
https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/151780/NL_Guidelines_EN.pdf

Guidelines for gender-inclusive language in English:
<https://www.un.org/en/gender-inclusive-language/guidelines.shtml>

TONE OF VOICE EXAMPLES

DO

DON'T

Dear sir/madam,

IN-HABIT is helping marginalized people in Cordoba. We are promoting IHW through strategic investment with the creation of a green, creative space in the city centre. Find out about this inclusive initiative here.

WHY?

- Talks about IN-HABIT in third person
- Uses US English (marginalized)
- Uses acronym IHW without an explanation
- Doesn't use contraction 'we're'
- Includes unnecessary details
- Language is too formal, not personal

DO

DON'T

Dear sir/madam,

I'm writing to request your assistance for our project in Nitra. We would like you to support our cause to begin construction on an 8 kilometer cycle track.

Our vision is the eventual creation of a bicycle link between the industrial park and Dražovce and the main city, and it will cost between <PRICE> and <PRICE>.

This is far beyond our means, therefore, we are asking for assistance from <ORGANISATION / DONOR>s in the area.

Yours sincerely,
<NAME>

WHY?

- Doesn't focus on what the project will achieve.
- Sir/madam is outdated and overly formal.
- 'I'm writing to...' is unnecessary; the reader already knows you're writing!
- It doesn't explain the background around the project – so why would this person help?
- Language is unnecessarily complex and formal.
- Numbers below 10 should be spelled.
- UK spelling – 'kilometre', not 'kilometer'.
- Does not tell the reader what it would like them to do at the end.

DO

We've been partnering with <PARTNER> in Nitra, Slovakia to create an eight kilometre cycle track linking the industrial park and Dražovce district with the main city. Find out more...

DON'T

Because of congestion, public services provision and inclusion, the promotion of alternative modes of transport like cycling is being invested in by the municipality of Nitra.

WHY?

- Messaging doesn't focus on a solution
- Does not provide the audience with a practical insight into what is happening in the city
- Uses passive tense, not active

DO

Lucca is investing in animal welfare to promote wellbeing for its citizens. Find out how initiatives like the Cohabitation Human-animal Regulation are helping. <https://bit.ly/lucca>

#inclusivehealthandwellbeing #animalwelfare #INhabiTowns

DON'T

Relevant resources have been increasingly invested in by the municipality of Lucca for improving the wellbeing of its inhabitants, and one such initiative is Cohabitation Human-animal Regulation which receives its funding from a range of EU-mandated investment bodies.

WHY?

- Uses passive tense, not active
- 'Relevant resources' is vague and unclear
- It's too long and filled with unnecessary details
- No call-to-action or hashtags

CONTACT

GET IN TOUCH

BOOK ON A TREE

General inquiries

projects@bookonatree.com

Press & Communication

press@bookonatree.com

Website

inhabitweb@bookonatree.com

Social media

inhabitsocial@bookonatree.com

Annex 3. European Commission references on Communication & Dissemination

COMMUNICATING YOUR PROJECT- H2020 ONLINE MANUAL

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT

<https://ec.europa.eu/easme/en/section/communication-toolkit>

EUROPEAN COMMISSION VISUAL IDENTITY

https://ec.europa.eu/info/resources-partners/european-commission-visual-identity_en

H2020 PROGRAMME GUIDANCE

Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

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